

**The Pashtunwali's Relevance as a Tool for
Solving the "Afghan Crisis"**

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This report is a "living document" and will undergo further expansion. Part of this will be necessary updating to take into account new facts and constellations as they evolve. Nevertheless, the value of the analysis put forward in the following pages extends beyond the specific current Afghan/South Asian conundrum. Regardless of whether the policy-relevant advice presented herewith will be heeded or ignored by Western (and Afghan) decision-makers, this analysis also has intrinsic value in that it represents a case study of the relevance of socio-cultural factors for conflict dynamics and the design of related military interventions. In addition to the military side of things, it also has tremendous implications for the framing of sustainable interventions in the realms of political and economic governance, as well as socio-economic development programming, the design of related projects, and their respective operationalization in terms of implementation and oversight modalities.

The socio-anthropologically informed dissection of the case of the ongoing and likely continuously escalating military intervention in Afghanistan is a tragic tale of cultural misunderstandings and misinterpretations. We hope that these lines can contribute to a better understanding of what is going wrong and why, and how the West can avoid doing more harm than good by implementing ill-devised policies.

The US administration is about to make decisions on its future course in Afghanistan. These decisions will have immense implications not only for the future of both countries but for the entire world. We contend that a decision in favor of increasing Western and specifically US troop levels would likely result in more harm than it would do any good. At the same time, we argue that the US would be well advised to bankroll a formidable reconstruction effort along the lines of a socio-economic Marshall Plan, for Afghanistan (with a focus on the south of the country), ideally also including at least the northwestern parts of Pakistan. Cross-border economic planning that combines elements of security, governance, and socio-economic planning is needed.

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NOTE OF THANKS AND INTRODUCTION

I would like to express my sincere thanks to the American Institute of Afghanistan Studies at Boston University for granting me financial support under the John F. Richards Fellowship Program. Without this support the present work could likely not have been finalized in 2008, if at all. I am more than grateful for the guidance of my teacher Christian Sigrist as well as all the ethnographers who did the actual fieldwork in the “tribal areas”, especially Ibrahim Atayee, Willi Steul and Mountstuart Elphinstone. I regret a lot that I was not able to get in touch with Ibrahim Atayee whose work is key to the present analysis.¹ Atayee’s “A Dictionary of the Terminology of Pashtun’s Tribal Customary Law and Usages”² is by far the most extensive description of the elements the Pashtunwali is composed of. Further kudos go to my friends and (former) colleagues Sabir H., Eisa and Ahmed Shah for their insightful comments and help in fixing some of the terminological issues contained in Atayee’s material.

In the existing German and English literature on this specialized subject as well as in the scores of Afghanistan-related scientific and non-scientific studies, reports and books which I have read since 2001, I did not find a single reference to his compilation. That Atayee’s work remains virtually unknown to the interested public is probably due to the fact that it was published in 1979, that is at the onset of the mujahideen’s Holy War against the PDPA regime and its Soviet backers. In addition, Atayee’s work was published by a governmental unit that fell into oblivion, which also contributed to Atayee’s work never getting

¹ According to a source whom I could not meet directly, a gentleman who claimed he worked with Atayee in a professional capacity in the 70’s, Ibrahim Atayee died of natural causes about a decade ago.

² Translated into English by A. Mohammad Shinwari; Kabul: International Centre for Pashto Studies, Academy of Sciences of Afghanistan, 1979.

known.³ I found a single copy of Atayee's work in 2005, in Kabul's ISAF bazaar and saw a small stack of them at the bookseller of Kabul's shop at the margin of Shar-e-Naw. An internet search for Ibrahim Atayee referenced his name as co-author of an ethnological research study published by a research outfit in Lahore, in the 1980s. According to an ex-colleague of Atayee he died in the late 90s.

The idea to edit and rearrange Atayee's material was triggered when I realized in early 2007 that many of the concepts described by Atayee helped enormously in making sense of the structural and behavioral idiosyncrasies I had myself encountered during my five years of work in Afghanistan and kept running into when extensively reading studies on Afghanistan in the course of my dissertation work. Looking at the various phenomena through the "tribal lens" of Atayee's material helped to decypher many current "historical facts", political constellations, and concrete behavior that previously seemed outlandish, strange, often bizarre or simply inexplicable.

In spite of the shortcomings in the English translation for which Atayee cannot be held responsible his dictionary can be considered an uncut gem. I hope to do his work justice by cross-referencing it with Willi Steul's landmark study. By doing so, I hope to have laid the groundwork and indeed to have contributed to a more in-depth understanding of the Pashtuns' tribal code of social regulation and code of honor as well as the underlying norm sanction complex.

My attempts in rendering Atayee's dictionary accessible to the public are not only based on the goal to inform academic theoretical legal and cultural studies. In the current context this socio-anthropological material is of the utmost importance in understanding the dynamics unleashed by yet another round of large-scale systemic interventions. My hope is that this analysis will convince Western

³ There is but one non-scientific source on the internet listing 178 of the 378 terms. It was evidently either OCR text-scanned or manually entered. Additional spelling mistakes were added to the ones present in Atayee's text with a few of the most obvious ones of the original having been corrected. In some cases the original text was changed either by omitting or by adding sentences.

decision makers that the wise thing to do is to approach the fighting enemy from the socio-cultural tribal angle instead of “taking the fight to the enemy” by outsourcing fighting al Qaeda to tribal militias. As such, I would like to dedicate this study not only to Ibrahim Atayee, but in a broader sense to the tribal Pashtuns. After all, better understanding of the other furthers peaceful relations and prevents harm from being done. May this work help in preventing further unnecessary bloodshed on all sides! I trust Mr. Atayee would subscribe to this application of his research.

The study of Atayee’s work has proven Sigrist’s and Steul’s dictum that the *Pashtunwali* is much more than a mere code of sanctions. It is not only a framework containing guiding principles and ethical commandments based on an architecture of action-oriented values, but it also captures and provides guidance for a specific way of life. The non-legal aspects (not covered by the “narkh” complex) are part and parcel of the code of regulation. It permeates social behavior and interaction at various levels.

The *Pashtunwali* is a blueprint for leading an honorable way of life in the specific socio-ecological niche shaped by historical influences comprising the human factor, it is an encompassing “ideology”.⁴

The concept of “sar“ (Pashtun: mar) or “head“ forms an intriguing dialectical counterpoint to the notion of an acephalous society. Rather than being head-less,

⁴ numerous invasions throughout the centuries; need to develop a fighting culture; specialization in waging war; tradition of fighting wars by proxy and mercenarydom; birth of the concept of Afghan/apagan through merit on the battlefield shown by mercenaries on the payroll of a Persian king; the geo-physical environment (mountainous strongholds, agriculture, harsh living conditions)

the segmentary structure is subject to dynamics of swarm- or network-like multiple if not potentially countless heads that might temporarily be subject to a hierarchical structure in situations of adversity but will fall back into its segmentary, multi-cephalous pattern at any given moment.

In view of the above, the Taliban movement cannot be decapitated. Even if Mullah Omar were a charismatic leader (which he is actually not, according to informed sources) he would still be easily replaceable. Pondering the lacking clear structure or hierarchy of the Taliban is as vain as painting them as a monolithical block. It can be assumed that the Taliban are in reality organized in non-hierarchical acephalous segments. While there are nominal figureheads and senior propagandists like Haqqani, the larger and smaller units are likely organized in acephalous fashion.

Pashtunwali functions as a latent code that is energized and becomes apparent in situations of stress or discord, be it at the micro, meso or macro level. Given the family-centeredness of Pashtun tribal life as well as the segmentary character of Pashtun society, even the micro level conflict can always be framed as external conflict against the other, or the “outside world”. The code literally keeps everybody constantly alert not to overstep invisible boundaries or, in the allegorical sense of representing the “Way of the Pathans” (Spain), serves as guiding principle and moral framework to ensure that an individual will not stray off his or her path, but go about things “in the right way”. All the above leads us to the hypothesis that the tribal code thrives when segments of Pashtun society are put under stress.

From a systemic research perspective, evolutionary mechanisms can also be applied to studying the robustness, resilience and flexibility of social ensembles. Contrary to the prediction of a (rapid) demise of (the remaining) aspects of *Pashtunwali*, it appears that the higher the outside pressure, the more reified and energized these traditional mechanisms become. At least this is the diagnosis from the outside based on the system’s detectible reactions at the outside.

Looking back at what happened to refugee communities in the context of the anti-PDPA jihad, (as well as in typical first generation immigrant households from traditionally male-dominated societies), it is not only a fall-back unto familiar, known patterns but an exacerbation of these patterns' most conservative aspects. The mechanism is always similar: "re-grouping the troops", defensiveness/passive-aggressiveness toward the outside, strong regime toward the inside based on value and moral-driven agenda. ⁵

There is a mechanical, automatic preformatted reaction to threats or attempts to force a concession, as could be seen in exemplary fashion when the US demanded that bin Laden be handed over, in blatant ignorance of the principles of *melmastya* and *melmapalana*, thereby actually forcing the Taliban to further protect bin Laden although they were at the point of actually expelling him from the country regardless of 9/11. Since the code's logic immediately kicks in by triggering a defensive reaction against threats. Hence, the more outside pressure

⁵ As James W. Spain puts it in the preface (page ix) to his book "The Pathans of the Latter Day", Oxford University Press 1995: "Still, I suspect that my contribution, for whatever it is worth, lies primarily in looking at the same things twice forty years apart. In most cases my conclusion is that more has remained the same than has changed. That in itself says something about the Pathans." Referring to Collin Davies he says (page 42): "Davies gave pukhtunwali its due, dividing it into three main tenets, which have persisted in the literature ever since: badal, revenge; melmastia, hospitality; and nanawati, submission or asylum. In the 1950s I asked as many Pathans as I could about this definition and they all confirmed it. In the 1980s and 1990s, I asked again and they said the same thing in almost the same words, although one cynic added, not altogether untruthfully, that the best badal is 'to have your servant shoot your enemy in the back'." Spain uses the urdu term *pathan* that subsumes ALL the Psthun and Pakthun tribes.

is applied (for or against whatever tribal Pashtuns decided), the lesser the chances for emancipatory change.

In the form of ethos (philosophy of being) and habitus (practical conventions of standardizing behavior in given contexts and situations), the duality between norms and related positive and negative sanctions is ever-present and regulates social interactions between tribal individuals and groups.

Nothing is wronger than to qualify the tribal Pashtun areas as lawless. Sharia and Pashtunwali have traditionally served as the tribals' code of jurisprudence and social regulation.⁶

The code is intrinsically geared toward males and has a strong component of commodifying females. This should be taken into account when mapping out development goals and related strategies for a New Deal. Tribal areas need to be given the opportunity to decide for themselves at which speed they want modernization to progress from a given level of departure to a new level/state in what time. If a community including its females decide by majority that they prefer opting for a lesser speed and lower level of modernization they should be given the possibility to do so.

There being a pro-Karzai and an anti-Karzai camp among the Pashtuns is part of the binary logic (tor-gund complex i.a.) of segmentary societies. This concept is intimately linked to the notions of status envy (siyali) and tarborwali (cousin rivalry). Any perceived advantage for a peer will normally be challenged. Hence,

⁶ The International Legal Foundation gives useful information on the current use of customary laws in Afghanistan in a report from September 2004, www.TheILF.org

if the intended Afghan Surge intends to co-opt and form alliances with specific tribal factions against those supporting the insurgency, the effort is doomed to failure, since adversity is the flip side of any selective, partial alliance, and the Taliban are masters in tribal power politics and forging of alliances (they even managed to outplay Hekmatyar in their original ascent to power). If to the contrary it was designed to team up with the Taliban to oust unwanted foreigners, success might be feasible. This would be tantamount to the Taliban switching sides which would be in line with the tradition of shifting alliances.

The concept of *nanawate* represents a window for negotiating a peace deal with the Taliban. For the Taliban to participate in negotiations, there must be, first and foremost, a neutral location, an independent mediator, a basic agreement on the conditions of a truce and a generally defined commonly shared, broad goal. This means that neither the Western nations nor President Karzai can make any conditional offers, nor unilaterally select the mediator and location. Western nations need to realize that trying to impose their solutions and procedures will ultimately be counterproductive and delay a sustainable and peace-bringing solution. An exit-strategy and a sustainable vision for the future needs to be “multilateral” and “democratic”, including all regionally important stakeholders (in that sense it must decidedly be non-Western, non-NATO).

1.WHY STUDY THE PASHTUNWALI?

The current Afghanistan problem is mainly based on the southern Pashtun crescent. To study the Pashtun tribal code of social regulation and honor is timely in a context in which almost all Taliban fighters and their leadership are ethnic Pashtuns. Although not all ethnic Pashtuns are Taliban one can still assume that most Pashtuns socialized outside Kabul and including those in high-level positions, are marked in demeanor, reasoning and action by the ethical precepts (ethos/habitus) of the Pashtunwali, regardless of whether or not they are aware of it.⁷ The above leads to the following logical sequence:

- 1)The tribal Pashtuns' way of life is governed by Pashtunwali.
- 2) Most Taliban are tribal Pashtuns observing Pashtunwali.
- 3) The current administration is led by a Pashtun from Kandahar, President Hamid Karzai, who is familiar with Pashtunwali.

Referring to Ibn Khaldun's proto-sociological theory⁸ a number of contemporary anthropologists such as Gellner have argued that in traditional societies of the

⁷ Other than among a specific culture's intellectual social symbol and structure analysts, in traditional societies usually to be found among the elders, it is quite atypical for any given "commoner" to be aware of the habitu(alization)s conditioning individual behavior, actions and reactions shaped by the given cultural context. To what extent socio-economic context fashions culture and vice versa as well as to what extent "being" (be it cultural and/or socio-economic) determines consciousness and the other way around is the fundamental research question that culturally sensitive social scientists are the best qualified for in the age of globalization.

⁸ While Gellner studied the Berbers, Ibn Khaldun's proto-sociological observations and classifications are based on (Semitic) nomadic and semi-nomadic desert tribes. Even if theories of the Pashtun being a lost tribe of Biblical age are dismissed and the majority

region there is an on-going constant cycle of politically unspoiled warrior tribes capturing power to then undergo a steady decline. Corruption, decadence, immorality etc. are common accusations held against such elites. According to this model, the spiral of decadence invariably reaches the critical point where the regime becomes so weak that, lacking popular support, it is toppled by an uprising of the “morally pure and uncorrupted” who are steeped in the moral values of rural society. This, of course, is in many ways a generic blueprint for describing the history of political upheavals in Afghan history, back to the days of the first Durrani rulers. By adding a) a dose of unpredictability and the turncoat syndrome of shifting alliances,⁹ and b) the unholy trias of pillaging, wayfaring and extorting subsidies,¹⁰ one can pretty much read the political history of Afghanistan as an endless variation of the same theme, establishing a link between the protagonists of the 18th and early 19th century till today. Applied to contemporary politics, what is laid out above clearly fits the scenario of the fast and steady decline of the erstwhile mujaheddin heroes who, after a brief interregnum in the early 90s, ended up going down in flames due to internecine fighting. Fitting the theoretical scheme, the Taliban stylized themselves as simple, unsophisticated country folks and promised to establish the rule of

of contemporary Pashtuns are sedentary, there remains a clear-cut distinct gap between hill tribes and lowland tribes with regard to the degree of sticking to ancient traditions, the “cultural grammar” of their worldview and the very much practical semantics of socio-cultural (self-)regulation. Last but not least, there is still a sizeable nomadic population (the Kuchis) who are part of the Pashtun ethnos.

⁹ There are eery parallels between the antics of Fattah Khan (early 19th century) and a number of contemporary power brokers who specialize in alliance shifting. Whereas the comforts of historical distance make Fattah Khan's dexterity seem like a running joke in a black and white slapstick movie of yesteryear, the intra-Afghan great game continues before our eyes in the build-up to the 2009 presidential elections.

¹⁰ Michel Barry, excepting Elphinstone and his prescient analyses, is the first to have clearly spelled out these mechanisms as key ingredients of political power and typical modes of resource appropriation including the mechanisms of Afghan statehood.

(Koranic) law and Islamic virtuousness, fighting vice wherever it would crop up.¹¹ Karzai's own efforts to establish himself and his regime as a hallmark of virtuosity have not been crowned by resounding success. Be that as it may, his long-standing commitment to engage in peace talks with the Taliban goes back all the way to late 2001 and before his appointment as leader of the transitional state authority, in early 2002. It is based on his analysis that there are common grounds or at least partial overlap as far as procedural agreements are concerned, for all Pashtuns, be they Taliban or supporters of the government, or neither. The following is meant to express our support to this analysis but more than that, it is an attempt to bring to light on the one hand the deeply entrenched socio-cultural mainstays and to enunciate the theoretical scientific underpinnings of said phenomena and their interconnectedness with each other.

In any given society, social change is difficult to achieve without at least partially winning over the most sceptical groups. In Afghanistan, throughout the past century, modernization attempts championed by a wide gamut of regime types regularly failed to address concerns of those not in favor of democratic

¹¹ Reading the demise of the Taliban regime as an outcome of their own inbuilt contradictions, such as preaching against vice while a number of their rank and file were apparently indulging in the pleasure of dancing boys, might be more than rendering undue homage to Ibn Khaldun. Clearly, in their own eyes, the Taliban leadership's credibility as well as their martial prowess were at least up until fairly recently tainted if not seriously undermined by the practice of old men sleeping with young boys. This to the point of Taliban leadership issuing edicts against such practices early into their reign but also one and a half decades later, after having regrouped and come back in force after their ouster. – As the prevalence of pashtunwali, the dancing boy phenomenon clearly is more than a whim: to the contrary it seems to be a salient trait of southern Pashtun culture, particularly in and around Kandahar. We surmise that it became deeply enmeshed in cultural practice due to the interrelated semantics of the constraints of a warrior culture very much constantly on the move and at the ready (quite possibly introduced by the Macedonians) linked to lethal sanctions surrounding the chastity of womanhood (*pardah*).

emancipation, modernization and widespread social change. This caveat posed problems to the enlightened monarchies of Amanullah and Zahir Shah all the way to Daoud's post-monarchic state and the following Communist regime. While the mujahideen's post-Communist rule and the Taliban's Islamic Emirates represented a gap in these largely top down, state-driven modernization attempts, the thread was picked up in early 2002 by the Transitional Authority/State, with the process culminating in the current attempts to modernize the country by constantly testing the boundaries of what is feasible in an overall environment in which the urban youth seem in their majority desperate for social change and innovation while large parts of the political establishment and the rural population stick to traditional values.

In fact, the history of development efforts in Afghanistan attempting to speed up the modernization process by government-designed policies and programs is marred by constant setbacks and spectacular large-scale failures. Attempts to modernize Afghanistan and especially the conservative countryside, steeped in tradition and religiosity, have regularly backfired and often failed altogether. Throughout the past three decades Afghanistan has been a battlefield of geo-political forces trying to impose their rule either by proxy or directly. The most recent wave swaying from centrally-driven secular modernization (PDPA/Khalq/Soviet rule) to religious conservatism (Taliban rule) and since early 2002 back to contested state-driven modernization can by now be brandished the "Afghan 30 Years' War". These 30 years consist but of the latest segments of almost a century of swinging to and fro between state-driven modernization and conservative backlashes and thus represent the latest sequences of a process which started in the early 20th century during King Amanullah's rule.

In the eighth year of the post-Taliban regime, there is growing evidence that the anti-governmental insurrection is being amalgamated and strengthened rather

than weakened by the current overall intervention approach which remains heavily biased toward militarily engaging what are tagged “anti-governmental elements”. With civilian casualties rising, allies and citizens of the United States are increasingly questioning the rationale of the war effort in Afghanistan and by extension, the overall aid effort there. Meanwhile, the US under its new political leadership has decided to go farther down the path of all-out confrontation, opting for a surge in military presence and a forward approach of on-the-ground insurgency, all the while successfully pushing the new rulers in Islamabad to fight the Taliban by military means.¹²

This complex plot which has always been marred by numerous sub-plots (the infamous alliance-shifting so characteristic of Afghanistan which can also be explained by Pashtunwali). This presents clear traits of a zero sum game with various factions all vying for influence and power. From the vantage point of a neutral observer the United States is but one of the players involved, and its respective strategic interests are vying for prominence with and against those of other political entities, be they states (Pakistan, India, Iran, Russia, the United Kingdom and other European nations) or local groups each having their own distinctive agenda (various sub-groups of the Taliban movement, Muslim fighters from regions as far away as the Caucasus (Chechnya) or Xinjiang (Uighur rebels), Gulbuddin Hekmatyar’s group etc.).

Throughout the build-up to the US presidential elections both candidates stepped forward with comments about their strategic positioning vis-à-vis their military and development strategy for Afghanistan and Pakistan. The suggestions included

¹² Predictably, the violence has now spilled into what could be considered relative havens of peace, such as Lahore. Peshawar has seen a spate of suicide attacks and bombings while the Swat valley has been turned into a war theater, as of late spring 2009.

putting pressure on Pakistan's government to rout insurrectionists from tribal areas within the FATA, teaming up with local tribes to uproot al Qaeda, sending commandos across the Durand line to chase down specific individuals should intelligence prove their presence in the NWFP/FATA and Pakistan not take any action to apprehend them. Obama made good on his announcements that, he would "go after America's enemies and fight terrorists on their territory." Whether this will solve the problem or not, only the future can tell. The likelihood of the current military approach bogging down the US and its international and regional partners (including the government's of Pakistan and Afghanistan) in an unwinnable counter-insurgency is being denied by right-wing strategists. Others, including realists, claim that we are witnessing a repeat of Vietnam and in many ways also the Russian Afghanistan campaign.

While the I-ANDS moved forward into an underfunded ANDS reeling under the impossibility to meet the demands and expectations of provincial development planners, the much-touted "Marshall Plan" for Afghanistan has not yet materialized until now. All that is left of it is, for the time being, the concept initially known as "civilian surge": an influx of several hundred technical experts and advisors who are supposed to build capacity in programme and project implementation, mainly via the mechanism of the (militarily embedded) Provincial Reconstruction Teams.¹³ As of mid-2009, a substantial USAID aid package for

¹³ This approach was rebranded and is now being referred to as a civilian coordination or assistance programme. A possible reason for this name change might be the ambiguities contained in "civilian surge". After all, it is not supposed to be a (military) rise or uprising of Afghan civilians. Maybe the planners also realized that in reality, it is American civilians and reserve officers getting involved in this effort and not Afghans as the name initially evokes. Also, the distinction between a civilian surge and a tribal surge (using tribal militias against militants/insurgents/IEGs) is not immediately clear. After all, tribals are civilians, as well. To add to the confusion, the concept of a humanitarian surge, framed along the lines of a massive aid concept, entered the debate in early 2009. This term also seems slightly misconceived in that one might argue that what is needed is not so much more emergency aid (the term "humanitarian aid" points in that direction) but solid development work that goes far beyond and much deeper than

the tribal areas which was supposed to be implemented several years earlier never got out of the starting blocks for want of a reliable mechanism and partners capable and willing to administer the important sums (in early 2009, the sum proposed for the FATA amounted to \$750 million) in question.

We contend that in most if not all of the above struggle, strife, casualties and social friction could have been considerably lessened if not altogether avoided by paying attention to the way the locals “tick”. In the case of the Pathans or Pashtuns, who remain key, if not the key, to the “Afghan question”, their way (of life) can be summed up by the notion of *Pashtunwali*, a term which denotes the tribal code of honor, social conduct and regulation, as well as the related customary legal framework prescribing positive as well as negative norms and sanctions which the honorable Pashtun individual, sub-clan, and clan, is bound to observe within any given social inter- or transaction, amongst themselves and vis-à-vis foreigners.

By continuing to ignore *Pashtunwali* either wilfully or in its innocent sense of simply not knowing, any given attempt to impose a foreign will is likely to at best evaporate and at worst trigger a massive reaction. This will lead to a setback not only of the initiative but more importantly, a loss of what little progress toward emancipation (female condition, girls’ education, human rights etc.) has been made at grassroots level. In dealing with or addressing their most conservative groups and members, proper understanding and respect of the emic rules and regulations of the Pashtun tribesmen is of the essence.

superficial patch-up jobs. In fairness, this is undoubtedly what is meant by many if not all of the proponents of the humanitarian surge. My critique targets the name, and by no means the concept of long-term socio-economic development of which I am a fervent supporter. – In the final analysis, this surge, be it called as it may, increasingly blurs the lines of civilian and military aid efforts, by means of PRTs (apparently, the TA or technical assistance will comprise a large number of reserve officers, not only to train Afghan police and military but also to implement aid efforts).

Any kind of intervention in a given social system has multiple side effects. Those effects are sometimes more, sometimes less obvious. Those less obvious can only be decyphered if the emic perspective is understood. Understanding a specific societal context requires in-depth understanding and knowledge of the society's history, culture and social structure so the analysis is to the extent possible informed by an insider's view close to the actual emic perspective of, in the case of southern Afghanistan, a "tribal native".¹⁴ If a military intervention is partially or globally combined with civilian, humanitarian aid efforts then the degree of complexity of intended and unintended effects is further increased. What counts here is not the original intention of the intervention(s) but the actual perception by and impact on the system intervened in.

The case of Afghanistan and especially its South, as well as northern Pakistan, is increasingly regaining the attention of political decision makers and the media. In recent months the notion of "tribes" has increasingly moved towards center stage in the discussion on how to solve the "Afghan Crisis". The suggested strategy consists in teaming up with tribal militias and/or providing them with arms to

¹⁴ Even though my analysis is specifically geared toward "dissecting" the Pashtun culture I am using the concept "tribe" in the sense of a specific group with its own cultural code of myths, rituals, genealogy, and habitualized rules and regulations governing social in-group interaction (habitus) and out-group relations. This ensemble of socio-cultural references allows for a specific horizon of expectation or what in German sociology is called "Erwartungssicherheit", which roughly translates into "one knows what to expect in a given situation" for a given deed, or absence thereof. This reliability regarding reactions and consequences is tied to a specific group's moral and ethical code of conduct and, as part of this wider framework, its specific norm-sanction complex. Defined as such, a given in-group or "tribe" can be virtually of any numerical size, and it does not matter if one is looking at an ethnic ensemble in South Asia of several million people, a street gang society in a metropolitan area of the Western hemisphere or an insider culture with its own rituals and set(s) of do's and don'ts in modern institutionalized settings such as the stock exchange or European dynastical high nobility.

bolster their defensive and offensive capacity, to fight a) recalcitrant elements of the Taliban movement perceived as not being inclined toward negotiations and ultimately laying down their arms, b) “neo-Taliban” belonging to the nexus of mercenarydom, poppy industry and (neo-)patronage, as well as c) elements of al Qaeda. The rationale behind such an approach is that there are perceived benefits in seeking out and mobilizing allies amongst ethnic Pashtuns to achieve a remake of the military counter-insurgency strategy (“the surge”) realized in Iraq’s Anbar Province.

While it is not unlikely and to the contrary indeed more than probable that additional allies can be mustered, provided incentives (cash, arms) are offered, such a move would obviously represent an intervention into the military equilibrium or stalemate apparently reached between the opposing forces in late 2008. In the Pashtun tribal context¹⁵, which is known for the volatility of its alliances and what is described in the literature as a specific culture of shifting alliances, the shelf-life of deals struck needs to be approached with a considerable degree of caution. Touching the concept of military equilibrium is equivalent to touching the backbone of power brokering in the tribal context. This, of course, is what the idea of the “surge” is all about: namely tipping the power balance in favor of the pro-Western regime in Kabul by teaming up with tribal power brokers amenable to an incentives package.

The following analysis will expose the shortfalls of such an approach by pointing out predictable counter-productive effects and negative consequences. This fills the gap left by writers who do not refer to *Pashtunwali* at all or only in a

¹⁵ Deal-making in the ministerial environment in Kabul is also marked by a considerable degree of similar traits. This shows that ethnic Pashtun administrators are not only Persianized – Persian socio-linguistic concepts such as taarof and takiyah are of fundamental significance in that they are informing the communication style of both Pashto and non-Pashto administrators - but the reverse is equally true (non-Pashtuns became influenced by Pashtun culture).

folkloristic aside, as well as by more sophisticated researchers, who refer to Pashtunwali as a major influence to be reckoned with, without explaining what it actually means and why it is so important. Likewise, it will look at the desirability and possible modalities of development interventions through the “tribal lens”. By mining the work of social anthropological pioneers such as Atayee, Steul, Sigrist, Elphinstone etc. related decisions can be made and designs be formulated in a culturally appropriate, adequate way taking into account the cultural substrate still moulding the moral and behavioral habit(us) of especially, but not exclusively, the tribal Pashtuns.

2. SELLING OUT? – ANSWERING SOME “TOUGH QUESTIONS”

DISPELLING THE MYTH OF INTRUSIVE SOCIAL SCIENCE

Unless social research is designed expressly to address given social problems, the practical application of research findings to such problems generally requires additional effort. The present attempt to address the “Afghanistan peace issue” by looking at the Pashtunwali could be perceived as social engineering by stalwarts of pure descriptive ethnography (who tend to favor a course of withdrawing all Western military troops from Afghanistan). This criticism is based on the argument accusing the intervening forces of cultural imperialism. Be it explicitly or implicitly, the positions hold that *“the West (and in particular, the United States) should not interfere with Pashtun culture”* at all for fear of doing more harm than good. In the most extreme manifestation of such critique the call is for all Western interference in its present form, be it military or humanitarian, to be ceased immediately or handed over to local agencies (from the Afghan army to local NGOs and/or the UN). In a mitigated version the position asks that military support be entirely discontinued and the interventions of Western agencies be limited to humanitarian aid efforts, only.

In answering such criticism one could argue that the consequences of no interference at all would likely lead to more violence and bloodshed inside Afghanistan than a less drastic change to the intervention strategy. The explicit statements and implicit assertions contained in the anti-“cultural imperialist” position are less backed by evidence than a policy change bolstered by a robust

defensive military mandate during a transitory phase until a phase-out schedule can be envisioned.

Contrary to an idealistic approach positing that Pashtun culture should not be “tampered” with by analyzing its tenets to identify interfaces vis-à-vis modernizing social change (such as political decentralization, grassroots governance, female emancipation etc.) there is ample evidence that it has long lost its innocence vis-à-vis external influences and interactions with foreign cultures.

The above is underscored by the following:

(a) Even as unintrusive an interference as writing about the Pashtuns has historically led to the object (the Pashtuns) appropriating the tales about them to promote and foster their own legend. This shows an inherent robustness but also flexibility in the cultural domain. Being written about certainly will not do the Pashtuns any harm even if the object of analysis is their customary code of honor. To the contrary it is quite possible that Pashtuns themselves might benefit most from the ingredients of their “way of life”, namely the *Pashtunwali* being thoroughly documented and analyzed in writing. As the German ethnologist Glatzer and others have shown convincingly, the tribal Pashtuns’ reputation for untamed brute fierceness and combativeness was not only reified by Pashtun eulogizers (Pashtun “landay”¹⁶ and accounts written by Western colonial administrator-ethnographers) but also partially “constructed” by Pashtun nationalist poet-intellectuals who readily embraced the concept of the wild untamable warrior Pashtun/Patan as a means of preemptive disincentive, deterring potential invading forces from any military designs against them. This is testimony to Pashtun culture being a living construct with national stereotypes

¹⁶ Pashtun poetry; couplets sung by men as well as women.

submitted to exogenous as well as endogenous interests and forces shaping the idea of shared in-group characteristics.

(b) Pashtuns form thriving dynamic trade and business communities in the Arab Gulf area (U.A.E. etc.) and are themselves probably among the most internationally mobile and inter-connected ethnic groups in South Asia. This trade extends well beyond illicit drug and smuggling activities and covers financial services and logistical operations. Social change and geographical mobility are by no means alien concepts to the population in Pashtun rural, and hence tribal areas. Geographical remoteness does not necessarily equal socio-political backwardness. "Tribal" Pashtuns of humble origins have proven time and again that they can be just as astute at utilizing market forces, manufacturing mass consumption items, using modern means of communications for business purposes etc., in short: embracing modernity and globalization, as individuals of any other background.

(c) Arguing in favor of not interfering in any given culture to promote emancipation puts into question humanitarian interventions by any type of aid agency which pursues such loftier policy goals beyond the objective of saving lives. By implication, this would mean that humanitarian aid should not interfere with the sphere of human and especially, female rights, in a way abandoning women to battle for themselves in male-dominated, paternalistic traditional societies.

(d) The Pashtun tribal nation and its culture is itself a product of other previously existing socio-cultural groups and thus has its own roots in socio-cultural change.

(e) The concept of forcing its ways upon other people is by no means alien to Pashtuns, themselves. That the very term Afghan/apagan is based on Pashtun mercenaries' battle prowess in foreign lands (fighting for a Persian king) is a little-known fact. That Pashtun kings systematically bolstered their kingdom by

establishing colonizing outposts combining incentives and coercive means to have ethnic Pashtuns set up sentinel villages at the Northern margins of the Pashtun/Afghan kingdom should also be mentioned in this context. The Pashtuns' historically grounded inherent ethnic superiority complex (though conflicting with the contradicting factor of despising "decadent governing elites") combined with strategic as well as fighting prowess on the battlefield has always been the primary factor behind military victories. The latest manifestations of this factor were the Pashtuns' contribution to the anti-PDPA/Soviet/Communist jihad of the late 1970's and the 1980's; the emergence and rapid expansion of the Taliban phenomenon as of the mid-1990's (not everything can be explained by the facilitating catalytic factors of tactical, strategic and logistical ISI support and Arab financing); as well as the Taliban revival as of 2004/5 which we are still witnessing today.

(f) In addition, the very idea of preserving a culture, shielding it from any type of intervention, would mean to confine it to the status quo ante including all its downsides, that would need to be weighed against the benefits of preventing the potential downsides that might result from actually interfering or intervening by way of research and/or humanitarian aid. This point, of course, extends well beyond the specific case in question and is of concern for the general debate of whether or not the modern world should refrain from its messianic urge to bestow its emancipatory benefits such as health care, literacy, female socio-economic and political emancipation etc. to the few "untouched" native tribal groups that remain on this globe.

(g) Detractors of putting ethnographical data to use even for sustainable development purposes ought to acknowledge that any given ethnographical description by itself constitutes a potential intervention in the described system in that it might be put to use for direct interventions by third parties. There is always a risk of such a direct intervention resulting in effects and an impact unintended

by the original provider of analytical data, comprising even the most well-intentioned authors. This is the more so the less contact a given culture has had before. Even arm-chair applied ethnology cannot claim innocence from unintended interference since at least to some degree if not exclusively it is always based on data collected in the field. Also, seemingly unintrusive research methodologies such as participatory observation tend to have a far greater unintended effect on the observed interactions than it would appear at first sight, at least subliminally influencing how the agents “act” in the presence of an observer (the “locals” on stage performing (in the sense of Goffman) in the presence of an audience or camera/recording device, the latter represented by the researcher).¹⁷ There is simply no denying that social research is potentially sooner or later either directly or indirectly linked to concrete interventions affecting the object(s) or, in some cases, the subjects of a study; that even the most non-applied basic research, once published, can be put to use for any type of concrete interventions, be they military or humanitarian; and that in general there is no control from the researcher’s side over how data and information will be put to use in the future for concrete applications once research results are made accessible to a wider public. Even so and all the same, one must concede that any type of intervention even in the most benign and well-intentioned shape, manner and fashion of international humanitarian and/or development aid often has unintended side effects, some of which can be outright negative. What might be (or be perceived as) positive for and by one group might actually turn out to be (or only be perceived as) negative for and by other involved individuals or groups. Actual impact and the mere perception of it ultimately amounts to the same effect. Even the most advanced ethics of emancipatory interventions cannot rule out harmful consequences.

¹⁷ Ethnographer Benedicte Grima describes the influence of her presence in Afghan villages in her book “Secrets from the Field”, Author House 2004.

RECALLING HISTORY

Asking Western support to cease wholesale, including humanitarian aid, ignores that the last time the West halted its (then almost exclusively covert) support through weapons provision and financial help to the Pashtuns and the Afghan nation as a whole—this was in the late 1980's, after the mujahideen had succeeded in prevailing against the PDPA regime—this decision had disastrous effects. The withdrawal was interpreted as abandonment by the mujahideen: they felt that they had been deliberately forgotten by the West after they had served their purpose, viz. draining Soviet financial and military resources and thereby weakening the primary antagonist to the United States in the Cold War. As a result, more than one former mujahideen-turned-Taliban or Taliban ally, feeling short-changed by their former Western allies, would turn against the West afterwards. Cutting all ties with Afghanistan would likely once again result in resentment and frustration among the current allies. Moreover, it would jeopardize all the emancipatory successes realized since the ouster of the Taliban regime at the beginning of the decade, spanning from female education to the modest achievements in the realm of institution and nation building.

Both the ultra-purist non-interventionist approach of withdrawing both foreign troops and aid agencies as well as the position of continued humanitarian support without Western troop presence tend to ignore that the potential consequence of withdrawing troops to “let the Afghans sort it out by themselves” is potentially leading to large-scale intra-Afghan fighting caused by the revival of factionalist warlordism with the consequence of a once again dramatically widening gap between the need for humanitarian aid and actual service delivery potential. Furthermore, with or without troop presence, Afghanistan is part of the

Great Game, be it on the global or regional scale. Regional players with geo-strategic interests of their own (Pakistan, India, Iran, also Russia and the neighboring Central Asian Republics, by extension of Turkmenistan also Turkey) will not refrain from intervening if the major Western nations (US, EU, Australia etc.) opt for turning their backs on Afghanistan.

Ending Western military presence would likely lead to a sea change setting back if not completely wiping out achievements in the realm of (female) emancipation with a large risk of further bloodshed and a time-warp back to the situation of the early 90's. Hence, putting an engagement of the Taliban on a non-military track is likely the most productive avenue worthwhile pursuing. The conclusion is that the presence of the international community is entirely justifiable and desirable as long as emancipatory goals are being pursued and military operations are limited to a sustainable minimum. This position acknowledges that downscaling military operations without real negotiations with the opposing side can also have counterproductive and ultimately unsustainable effects.

IN FAVOR OF "REVERSE SOCIO-LEGAL ENGINEERING"

Buzkashi is a team sport in which opposing sides mounted on horseback battle over the "ball" which has to be snatched and deposited in a demarcated area that represents the adversary's goal line. The game is quite violent, especially if played according to traditional rather than "Olympic" rules.¹⁸

¹⁸ A defined number of horses, two clearly defined and discernible teams wearing uniforms of a specific type, rules for substitution of players, exactly defined length of time for play inclusive break, delimitation of playing field in space, specific

In essence, traditional rules are “no holds barred”, with the main rule being that there are not many rules. The idea is to score while at the same time trying to prevent the other side from doing so. Kicking, bruising, clobbering, lashing the opponents are staple features of traditional *buzkashi*. There is no clear delimitation of the playing field, nor of the playing time, nor of the number of players, who can phase in and out of the game according to their whim and fancy (the number and quality of the contestants riding for a side often being in direct correlation to the spending power of the sponsor, who might be a traditional *khan* or a warlord). *Buzkashi* is often referred-to as the Afghan national sport.

This, in a way, is highly misleading in that it is only endemic to the northern part of the country (Kunduz, Badghis, Badakhshan, Balkh etc.). It is largely an Uzbek and Tajik speciality, with some northern Pashtuns and Hazaras also playing it. Rural Pashtuns (Taliban) do not indulge in this pseudo-national pastime.

At the same time, *buzkashi* imagery still renders itself for capturing essential traits of the current situation in that non-*buzkashi* players (Taliban) are watching as the *buzkashi* over political and administrative power is going on between Kabul and the northern parts of the country, as well as within the rentier state’s administration and political institutions.

In the metaphorical sense, after all, sometimes, there is a clear playing field when it comes to political and/or military power struggles; likewise, the number of players and which side they are on is sometimes very clear, and so is the duration of the match. But most often this is not the case. The image is perfect for conveying the current situation of the entire country and its various on-going struggles over power and influence at the various political and geographical levels.

rules of how to score and of fouls inclusive penalties, referee applying the rules etc.

In this sense, it is quite obvious that the insurrection/insurgency plays according to the traditional set of rules, while the administration in place as well as the West would prefer playing according to Olympic rules or pretend not to be involved in the game at all. So in reality what is presently going on is a grand no-holds-barred old-school traditional *buzkashi*.

The political elites of the West are slowly awakening to this fact with some critical voices appearing even among the military.

To avoid the fate of the Soviet Union with Gorbachev calling for a hasty retreat, subsequent hand-over with a scaling down of external support and the consequence of yet another round of internal *buzkashi* (the civil war years in the early 1990's) there are some lessons to be learned.¹⁹

1) avoid that the home team suffers a rout by realizing that the *buzkashi* being played follows traditional rules

2) stop pretending that the Olympic style *buzkashi* played by the home team can ever prevail over the team playing according to traditional rules

3) study the hidden do's and don'ts of the traditional style *buzkashi*. A better understanding of traditional techniques can be used for scoring more points and winning the game. The question is whether winning means outscoring and crushing the opponent or calling it a tie, officially ending the game and letting everybody enjoy the post-game party.

The undesired alternative scenarios would be

(1) being defeated oneself

¹⁹ Entering the academic arena of Afghan *buzkashi* from a meta-perspective, Immanuel Wallerstein recently referred to Brzezinski's related analysis of Afghanistan potentially becoming a 2nd Vietnam for the US; to be found on Wallerstein's homepage <http://www.iwallerstein.com/>.

(2) abandoning one's allies on the field to see them "torn to pieces" along with the *buz* (the Afghan state);

or: (3) getting bogged down in a never-ending game roaming from field to field in Sisyphean efforts where riders and horses run themselves rugged and tired, those riders fading away in exhaustion or disinterest being replaced by a constant stream of new, freshly-motivated opponents and the *buz* gradually being shredded to pieces until there is no carcass left to fight over.

It is necessary to study the *Pashtunwali* to determine how one can shape support to existing mind-sets, cognitive frameworks and modes of social regulation. In other words, innovations introduced from outside will need to be adapted. Related interventions would need to match or at least not represent too much of a change vis-à-vis the existing local "operational speed" encompassing all spheres of the way of life as well as inherent dynamics related to the society's capacity or inherent proneness toward social change. Rather than forcing accelerated development upon a society which might not be ready or willing to receive such support, interventions should be refrained from if not asked for.

"DO NO HARM" REVISITED

The moral dilemma of trying to defend a "doing no harm" approach in the realms of humanitarian aid and institution-cum-nation building by means of military force as well as the radical "all troops out now" position has been pursued ever since the early stages of the post-Taliban phase. Up until today, military and political decision makers occupying leadership positions in their countries consistently failed to realize that there is an alternative route which remains largely

unexplored, consisting of redefining the military mission to assertive-defensive presence and reframing the developmental as well as political support according to a logic of (non-hierarchical, decentralized/democratic) inclusiveness. Gradually, there are critical voices in Western diplomatic, military and political circles who question pursuing the militarily driven approach of trying to defeat the enemy on the battlefield and advocate a negotiated settlement with the Taliban directly or indirectly acknowledging that the best option might be to settle for a compromise with the insurgent forces.²⁰

However, what is lacking is an understanding of procedural options about how “negotiations” with the current detractors of the regime in place could be framed; a concrete vision of what an inclusive redefined technical support package for Afghanistan could look like, content-wise; and an approach to shape inclusive ideas for increased levels of Afghan governance and administrative implementation capacity of civil services and aid programs, framed in terms of novel constitutional and institutional arrangements. The above package would inform the strategy for an incremental phase-out of Western military support in that it would render troop presence increasingly unnecessary. The foundational groundwork for all of the above is laid in the following analysis of the Pashtunwali’s inherent moral code, its content, structure and procedural logic.

The line of reasoning “Whom better to ask than an Afghan?” (expert X) is naïvely essentialistic in that it equates an unspecified Afghan-ness with automatic understanding of underlying structures of Afghan society. It disregards the complexity of Afghan society that one cannot innately “understand” by having been born in the country. For that matter, there are also experts belonging to one

²⁰ Related examples are General McKiernan’s speech delivered to the Atlantic Council (Council’s Commanders Series, November 18, 2008) and the press leakage involving British and French diplomats.

of the ethnicities in Afghanistan who have not been socialized in Afghanistan. A final objection to the essentialistic argument is that Afghan intellectuals, “native” or not, might be inclined to sway in a certain direction of political, cultural and/or ethnic affiliation in analyzing the situation which might affect their ability to be an impartial analyst and arbiter.

“Are only Afghans really qualified to comment on Afghan issues? Are outsiders/non-Afghans not qualified to comment on Afghan issues? “

The answer would be: For both Afghan and non-Afghan analysts, the same rules apply; if they have studied Afghanistan’s history and political issues, both are qualified to comment as long as they are aware of their own limitations in terms of insight and understanding and describe their methodology and specific research approach, i.e. how the data analyzed was collected, data caveats etc. Having an Afghan background without having studied the issues is not a valid qualification and might actually be a major impediment in terms of judgmental bias. Either way, intellectual humility calls for framing applied research findings as suggestions spelling out possible side effects rather than presenting ready-made solutions.

3. METHODOLOGY APPLIED TO RENDER ATAYEE'S MATERIAL ACCESSIBLE

In his compilation of concepts related to or comprised in the tribal code of honor, Ibrahim Atayee organized the material in alphabetical order. In many cases there are remarks which are either embedded within the explanations of listed key items or which appear at the end of the respective explanatory notes, anecdotal evidence and descriptions based on his field notes. However, Atayee did not present systematic sub-lists of the concepts arranged by logical categories. The *Pashtunwali* neophyte is often at a loss about how a specific concept or term fits into the overall picture.

The methodology I applied to organize Atayee's material followed the following steps:

1. Intense study of the entire body of terms and concepts to grasp the implicit structure of the code based on its internal logic.
2. Identifying key concepts and mapping them in logical order with cross-references.
3. Mapping of every single item (concept's term) with related brief description to build an overall architecture.
4. Physical mapping of hand-written notes on Atayee's 378 items. The conversion of this visual representation into a printable, reader-friendly

format is foreseen as a follow-up project on the way forward toward an academic publication.

5. The original text of Atayee's material which only existed as hard copy was retyped into the computer to render the material organizable by logical sequence (Again, Atayee presented his terms in one meta-list in strict alphabetical order). Along the way, spelling and grammar were improved wherever appropriate.²¹ The transcription of Pashtun terms used by Atayee was largely adhered to with the exception of cases where he himself used different spellings of the same word.
6. The arrangement of terms by logical sub-categories (lists) was carried out for orientation purposes so one can seize the underlying logic of the system. While the arrangement is logically coherent a number of overriding terms such as *sharm* and *namus* apply in a number of subcategories in similar or slightly varying technical meaning.
7. In the sub-categories (list) the terms are often assorted in groups, sometimes with a title. This is not meant to be an unalterable order but rather a help for the reader to grasp the relation.
8. In frequent cases, a given term appears in more than one list. Concrete technical concepts such as those pertaining to the enforcement of sanctions (reparations and penalties comprised in the *narkh* complex) and procedural regulations linked to reconciliation and the passing of a judgment (*maraka*, *jirga* linked to the *nanawate* complex) are always based on ethical and moral concepts (*namus*, *Pashtunwali*, *tura*) which again are all invariably linked to the aggressive and/or competitive side of

²¹ To the extent possible, the flavor of the original translation was preserved. In a limited number of cases where Atayee made extensive use of relating specific terms to proverbs or sayings, the exact meaning of Atayee's comments could only be guessed about.

the code of honor (*badal, siyali, tarborwali* etc.). As such, the presented cross-referencing should be understood as one of many possible ways to represent the interrelation of the terms. Alternative representations are also possible that would have specific terms appear more often, or less often, i.e. in more or fewer lists than is the case in the system presented hereafter.

9. In a number of cases a given concept will have a different or an alternate name in other geographical areas; on the other hand the same term can have slightly different conceptual content according to the area. Where this is the case, Atayee duly pointed this out.
10. Whenever a specific concept appears more than once, then the name of the other lists where it appears is referred to in the column on the left-hand side of each term. If there is no reference in the left-hand column this means that the term only appears in the respective list where it is mentioned.
11. On the right-hand side of each term there is an abbreviated or translated version of the specific term presented by Atayee. Further to the right appears Steul's comment related to the same term in all those cases the same term was discussed by both authors. Steul's comments sometimes slightly vary from Atayee's version. Comparing the two versions adds depth and perspective to the material.
12. In the list "Steul" terms presented by Steul which did not appear in Atayee's booklet and additional information are presented. They are (still) presented in German.
13. In the dictionary lists, Steul's comments (still) appear in their original German version.
14. The dictionary lists all terms and concepts in full length in the exact alphabetical order of the original material presented by Ibrahim Atayee.

The dictionary is NOT included in this document, it will be available online on www.educationinafghanistan.com by the end of october 2009.

4. LEXICOLOGY

SUB-LISTS			
<p>The following lexicographical listings map out the Pashtunwali's terminology by thematical groups. While the entirety of thematic clusters belong to the universe of concepts under the Pashtunwali, there is also a separate list by the same name combining the more overriding terms and key concepts, was well as general notions.</p>			
TABLE OF LISTS			
LIST	NUMBER OF ITEMS PER LIST	SUBTITLES	
PASHTUNWALI	75	yes	MAIN QUALITIES OF PASHTUNWALI, WOMAN (POSITIVE), WOMAN (NEGATIVE), MANLINESS, RELATIONS
MARAKA	75	yes	FRAMEWORK FOR MARAKA, LAW, REASONS, SETTLEMENT, EXPENSES, OATH, MEDIATION, CELEBRATION, NOT SATISFIED, ZADRAN TRIBE
GUILT	64	no	
TAWAN	55	no	
ORGANISATION OF SOCIAL LIFE	54	no	
JIRGA	44	no	
NANAWATE	44	no	
ORGANISATION IN VILLAGES	35	no	
PREKRA	31	no	
WOMAN	29	no	

MURDER	28	no	
NARKH	23	no	
WEDDING	18	no	
LOW SOCIAL STRATUM	15	no	
JAGRA	13	no	
MULLA	7	no	

LIST CATEGORY		SUB-LIST	
4.1.	Pashtunwali (Comprehensive Code of Conduct , Honor & Social Regulation)	4.1.1.	Pashtunwali
		4.1.2.	Organisation of Social Life
		4.1.3.	Organisation in Villages
		4.1.4.	Low Social Stratum
		4.1.5.	Woman
		4.1.6.	Wedding
		4.1.7.	Mulla
4.2.	Conflict / Escalation	4.2.1.	Guilt
		4.2.2.	Murder
		4.2.3.	Jagra
4.3.	Legal Framework / Sanctions, Penalties, Compensation	4.3.1.	Narkh
		4.3.2.	Tawan
4.4.	Judiciary & Legislative Functions and Fora	4.4.1.	Maraka
		4.4.2.	Jirga
4.5.	Reconciliation (Process)	4.5.1.	Nanawate
		4.5.2.	Prekra

4.1.

PASHTUNWALI (COMPREHENSIVE CODE OF CONDUCT , HONOR & SOCIAL REGULATION)

4.1.1.	Pashtunwali
4.1.2.	Organisation of Social Life
4.1.3.	Organisation in Villages
4.1.4.	Low Social Stratum
4.1.5.	Woman
4.1.6.	Wedding
4.1.7.	Mulla

4.1.1.	Pashtunwali, 75 items			
lists	number in dictionary		Atayee	Steul
		Main qualities of Pashtunwali		
	257	PASHTUN-WALI	all the customs, traditions, heritage, customary law and usages and all social relations, the concept conveying the socio-economic political and cultural system in totality	S.240, Weltbild, Wertvorstellungen, Summe sämtlicher Werte und daraus entwickelter Normen, die die spezifisch paschtunische Lebensart bestimmen, allumfassender Regulator für Bestand der Gesellschaft und Verhalten des Einzelnen
	117	GHAIRAT	zeal, a part of NAMUS	S. 137, „ghairatman“, Adjektiv für den „guten“ Paschtunen, der in der Beurteilung der Gemeinschaft als ein besonders vorbildliches Gruppenmitglied gilt
	203	MERANA	see GHAIRAT	

see WOMAN	223	NAMUS	literally „chastity“, in common usage it means woman	S.140 ff, indirektes und direktes NAMUS
	225	NANGA	to guard the courage, grace and generosity and other good qualities of Pashtunwali	S.137 ff, keine eigene Aussage, zitiert nur Janata usw. „nangialai“, mannhaft, mutig
	227	NARINA	the one possessing all the good qualities of PASHTUNWALI; the one who is generous, courageous, hospitable	
see NARKH	256	PASHTO	the language of the Pashtuns; figuratively it connotes truth and reality; the name of Pashtuns tribal law, customs and usages	
see GUILT, NANAWATE, TAWAN,	303	SHARM	literally means "shame". In tribal customs and usages it is a payment made by PAR (GRAM, MALAMAT), the one accused and proven guilty, to his opponent	S. 169, 170 Steul zitiert Janata/ Hassas 1975, die wiederum sich auch auf Kiefer, 1972, beziehen: „Das entschieden wichtigste Regulativ allgemeiner Umgangsformen...’Bescheidenheit, Schüchternheit, Schamhaftigkeit, Schande“, differenziert in ehteram (Ehrfurcht und Zuvorkommenheit gegenüber älteren und höhergestellten Personen sowie dem Gast) und ezat (Höflichkeit und Zuvorkommenheit gegenüber jedem Mann und jeder Frau),

				Schamgeld
see MURDER, NANAWATE, TAWAN	17	BADAL	literally „revenge“	S. 153, Vergeltung, Rache, Tausch
	236	NOOM	name, but in customary usages it connotes tribal repute	
		WOMAN POSITIVE		
see WOMAN	248	PARDA	literally „curtain“; it also means to save face; women's dress is PARDA	
	196	MAROSHA	a married woman	
	251	PARUNAY	PARUNAY, PORANY and TEKRAY are synonyms. Figuratively these words connote woman.	
	273	RASHTEYA	truthfulness, uprightness	
see WOMAN	326	TARLA	the daughter of a KAKA (uncle)	
see WOMAN	329	TEKRAY	see PARUNAY	
		WOMAN NEGATIVE		
see WOMAN	9	ARTINA, MANDINA	wife; adjective for the inferior one	

		MANDINA	
		MANLINESS	
	183	MERA	husband
	235	NIKA	grandfather
	220	MZAKA	land in general, but in particular it means the agricultural plot of one man; symbolically it represents one's ancestors
see MARAKA	259	PATKAY	turban, manliness, courage
	302	SHAMLA	each end of a turban; usually the upper end of the turban that stands erect over the head.; SHAMLA connotes GHAIKAT and MAIRONA
see JAGRA, TAWAN	377	ZIERA	beard; symbol of manliness
see JIRGA, MARAKA, MURDER, NARKH, TAWAN	365	WRATA	revenge, retaliation, retribution
	113	GHACH	revenge
	213	MOT	synonym to GHACH

see MARAKA, JIRGA, PREKRA	123	HOD	decision, resolution
	373	ZHABA	promise, undertaking, agreement
	151	KHABARA	oral pledge
	159	KHWLA	synonym to ZHABA and KHABARA
	12	ASIL	noble
		RELATIONS	
	5	AKA	uncle, an elder at the age of one's father
	315	SYAL	rival
	316	SYALI	rivalry
	325	TARBOR	those having a share in a common inheritance
	346	TRA	uncle
	101	DA WARMAIG DA WIENI SHARIKWALI	"common neck blood", i.e. blood relationships

see NARKH	16	BAD	literally „bad“; crime, offense	
	20	BADI	enmity	
	21	BADRAGA	a person or a group of persons escorting someone to be safe	S. 147, Geleitschutz, für Einzelne, aber auch Mittel, um unterlegene Gruppen im Konfliktfall vor der sicheren Vernichtung zu bewahren, daher Mittel der Friedenssicherung; Schutz für Schwache ist Forderung des NANG
	34	BEWASA	a person who lacks the material and spiritual means to carry his dispute with someone else to an end	
	108	DOSHMAN	enemy	
see JIRGA, MARAKA	119	HAD	bone, member of PLARINA	
see NARKH	171	LASHKAR	a group of armed men	
	219	MLATAR	one who cooperates	
	262	PEGHOR	sarcasm, shame	
	278	SALATA	when no-one is left in a family but an unzealous, coward and unmanly heir	

see GUILT	347	TRABGANAY	the cut-throat rivalry and enmity among members of the same PLARINA
	362	WINA	blood, all kinsmen, murder
	378	ZORAWAR	a man who evades the tribal customs
	1	AEL	tame, obedient and submissive
	13	ATAM	"food in general"
	14	ATAN	a Pashtun type of square dance done by men
	28	BARKHA	part or share, rights
	29	BASHAL	pardon
see JIRGA, NANAWATE, ORGANISATION OF SOCIAL LIFE	104	DODAY	bread, synonym to MARAY
see NANAWATE	253	PASA	sheep
see NANAWATE	177	LOKHAY	sheep given in NANAWATE; in Afridi tribes of Tiera it is a custom similar to BADRAGA (escorting)
	194	MARAY	meal

	201	MELMA	guest	S. 164, Melmapalana, ausführlichere Beschreibungen der „Gastfreundschaft“
	240	OJRA	a place for guests and also for gatherings and parties of the male population	S. 166, wird im Zusammenhang mit „melmapalana“ als hujra erwähnt
	232	NGHARAY	the hearth, the place in the home where fire is made	
	239	OR	fire	
	269	QURAN LOSTAL	to recite the verses of Quran	
	279	SAM	it closely conveys the concept of SPIN	
see NARKH	289	SPIN	anyone who has not committed an offense or crime	S. 54/55, Legende, wie es zu den Begriffen kam, Bezeichnung auch für Clans und Solidaritätsgruppen
	296	STANA	the God-favored and holy	
see GUILT, NANAWATE TAWAN	120	HADIRA	the graveyard and the grave	
see NARKH, TAWAN	331	TERAY	encroachments on the rights of others	S.216, terai, 1. jede Tötung eines Menschen, ob schuldhaft oder ohne

				<p>Verschulden, z.B. in einem Unglücksfall</p> <p>2. jede Körperverletzung (auch der Versuch), d.h. jede dauerhafte und nicht dauerhafte Einschränkung eines Individuums in seiner körperlichen Funktionsfähigkeit</p> <p>3. jede Ehrverletzung, d.h. der durch Aktionen oder verbale Äußerungen dokumentierte Zweifel an der moralischen und ethischen Integrität des Individuums oder Gemeinwesens</p> <p>4. jede Handlung (auch der Versuch) gegen die sexuelle Ehre einer Frau, d.h. Annäherung, unsittliches Betragen in ihrer Gegenwart, Verführung und Entführung einer verheirateten Frau- in diesem Fall zusätzlich Verstöße gegen die dem Ehemann ausschließlich zustehenden sexuellen Rechte</p>
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				5. jeder Eingriff (auch der Versuch) in die Verfügungs-, Eigentums- und Nutzungsrechte eines Individuums oder eines Gemeinwesens an einer Sache
	237	NOWGHAY	to disfigure something, a person or an animal	
	339	TOPAK	rifle	
	350	TURA	sword	

4.1.2.	Organisation of Social Life, 50 items			
lists	number dictionary		Atayee	Steul
	10	ASHAR	collective public work	
	11	ASHARBANAY	persons chosen for and participating in ASHAR	
see GUILT	22	BALANDARA	collective work, synonymous to ASHAR, its most usual meaning is "joint attack"	
	243	PAGAREY	collective work (in Paktya)	
	324	TAR	The collective decision to work collectively.	
	6	ANAMKHWARA	insulting name for people who do not participate in the WESH system	
	28	BARKHA	part, share, rights	
	242	PACHA	casting lots	

	286	SERAY-KHWARA	people who have a permanent piece of land which is excluded from the WESH system (Mohmand tribe)
see JIRGA, MARAKA	308	SHLAWAND	the act of determining the shares of the families (Helmand, Kandahar)
	358	WANDA	share, part
	361	WESH	distribution (land distribution system)
	8	ARBAKAY	a tribal policeman
	45	TSALWAIKHTY	group of armed men assigned to guard the forest
see JIRGA, NANAWATE, PASHTUNWALI	104	DODAY	bread; DODAY and MARAY are synonyms; MELMASTEYA (entertainment of guests); expenses of JIRGA
MARAKA, PASHTUNWALI	194	MARAY	meal, in particular a meal served to MARAKACHEYAN by well-wishers
	375	ZHRANDA	flour mill
see TAWAN	48	TSRAH	a single toiling man who leaves his home to find employment elsewhere (Pashtuns living between Kandahar and Ghazni)

see TAWAN	197	MASAPER	a man away from his homeland	
	238	OPRA	one who lives in a strange tribe where he has no land	
see JAGRA	54	CHIGHA	a call for help, or a call for collective work, usually by drumming	S. 149, „Trommler“, mit dem Trommelschlag wird angezeigt, wenn in der Nähe Schüsse gehört wurden, wenn irgendetwas vorfiel, das den Anschein einer Bedrohung erweckt hat. Cigha wird dann die Versammlung aller waffentragenden Männer genannt, die auf das Schlagen der Trommeln hin oder auf eine Aufforderung anderer Art zusammenstürzt, sofort zum Ort der Tat eilt und die Ursachen der ganzen Aufregung feststellt. Weiterlesen für interessante Fälle, im hinteren Teil Schilderung von Cigha im Einsatz
	61	DA CHEGHI DOOL	„the drum for calling“	
	74	DA LASHKAR CHEGHA	to call in the tribal army	
	86	DA NIME SHPI NARA	the midnight calling	
	98	DA TORE SHPAY CHEGHA	the midnight-call	

see JUGRA	105	DOL	a double-headed drum	
see JAGRA	106	DOLCHI	the DOL drummer	
	107	DOL DANGAWAL	to drum the DOL; the announcement of some imminent danger	
	230	NAYAK	a tribal armed man is called NAYAK	
	160	KHWLA KAGAWAL	A BEWASA (helpless) engaged in BADI (trouble) unable to carry it to the end, will call on his KHEL for help and will necessarily be helped.	
	254	PASA HALALAWAL	to slaughter a sheep in order to obtain help	
see GUILT	347	TRABGANAY	the cut-throat rivalry and enmity among members of the same PLARINA.	
	219	MLATAR	the one who cooperates	
	153	KHAN	KHAN is a MASHAR (elder) of the tribe.	S.68, mongolischer Ursprung „Fürst/König“, S.70 "Der khan/malek ist der erklärte Repräsentant der Autorität

				einer Gruppe, nicht jedoch Inhaber dieser Autorität. Die Macht eines khan wird gebildet durch die ihm persönlich eigenen Attribute - z.B. auf Grund seiner u.U. im Falle des khan vorhandenen ökonomischen Dominanz oder des ihm eigenen Potentials an physischer Gewalt - und die ihm durch die Anerkennung als khan/malek durch seine Gefolgsleute und die damit verbundene Unterstützung mögliche Durchsetzung."
	189	MALAK	MALAK is the elder of his tribe.	s.84/85, Malek = Khan, malek=der von der Dorfgemeinschaft gewählte Repräsentant der Kommune
see JIRGA, MARAKA	198	MASHAR	a respected title given to one by his tribe, de jure member of MARAKA and JIRGA	S.100/101, informeller Führer; Oberhaupt einer fraternal joint family; Männer mit „ghairatman“ und Landbesitz
	59	DA BAIRAGHONO SPARAL	to submit or to surrender flags	
	135	KALANTER	KALANTERAN have an active part in the protection of forests. The MIR and KALANTERAN together form an autonomous executive power having influence on MARAKA and JIRGA, too.	
	145	KASHAR	KASHAR means younger	

see JIRGA, MARAKA	206	MIR	a tribal MASHAR
	210	MIR DAMNA	salary of MIR
see JIRGA, MARAKA	282	SARKHEL	very close to MIR in meaning
	290	SPIN GIERAY	the elder, experienced respected member, often an advisor of his tribe
see PASHTUNWALI	34	BEWASA	a person who lacks the material and spiritual means to carry his dispute with someone else to an end
see JIRGA, MARAKA	336	TOIGH	the expenses of MARAKA
see JAGRA, TAWAN	269	QURAN LOSTAL	to recite the verses of Quran
see GUILT	100	DA WACH KHALI AKHISTAL	To take a dried woodchip; a kind of oath-taking in everyday common problems
	369	ZAIRAY	good news or bringing good news
	306	SHARA	to pray to have bad luck fall upon a person

4.1.3.		ORGANISATION IN VILLAGES, 35 items		
lists	number in dictionary		Atayee	Steul
	317	TABAR	a group of KHELs forming a unit	
	157	KHEL	ethnographic unit forming the central point around which the tribe moves	S.32/33 In Khost kein "common word" für die Benennung von patrilinearen Deszendenzeinheiten. Es wird auch der Begriff qawm verwendet. Wird in Khost im Sinne von "family" gebraucht.
	318	TAK	tribal territorial boundaries of each KHEL	
	137	KAM	a large unit in the social formation of a tribe	
	139	KANDAY	a small tribal local unit	
	141	KARRA	a large TABAR consisting of several big KHELs	
	263	PLARINA	unit of the tribe which has a common ancestral father	
	133	KAHOL	family	
	134	KALA	fortified high wall surrounding one or more houses	Lehmburg

	136	KALAY	A cluster of houses of a KHEL	
	359	WARSHO	any grazing land	
	47	TSARZAI	grazing land	
	165	KOT	military fort	
see JIRGA, MARAKA	24	BANDA	a temporary dwelling outside the KALA	
	166	KUDAKHA	a hut built from woods and stones	
	148	KAWDAY	a hut made of bushes and wood	
	163	KOR	domicile	
	103	DERA	any place in the open air for guests	
	280	SAMEL	an Afridi tribe	
	291	SPIN GUND	spin (white), a certain group of Pashtun tribes	S.54/55, spin and tor clans aufgelistet; angeblich entstanden aus Streit über Elster (mehr schwarz, mehr weiß?), Solidaritätsgruppen
	35	BITA	the brother of Tipa and Tilo, son of Karlan, Mezie is a branch of Zadran tribe and descendent of BITA	S. 54, Zadran ist bis auf wenige Ausnahmen spin
	334	TILO	a son of Karlan Nika, ancestral father of the Mangal tribe	

	335	TIPA	one of the two sons of Karlan Nika and the ancestral father of the Zadran tribe
	342	TOR GUND	a certain group of Pashtun tribes; tor (black), see SPIN GUND
	92	DA RAZMAK TSALOR NARKHEYAN	founders of Wazirs
	32	BAYRAGH	a tribal flag
	142	KARSHA	a line; it is the demarcation line between the territories of two or more tribes or KHELs or any two social units
	25	BANDAR	a meeting or a party
	202	MENA	home, homeland and country, a temporary camp of nomads
	150	KEGDAY	a tent made of goat hair
	275	RAW	the right of way of Kochis
see NANAWATE	214	MRAYAY	slave

	155	KHATAAWA	a place located in the suburbs of Gardiz, inhabited by Ahmadzais
	147	KATMIR	a big fire to announce a public event

4.1.4.	LOW SOCIAL STRATUM, 15 items			
lists	number dictionary		Atayee	Steul
	231	NAYEE	village barber	
	126	JAT	JAT make double drums, sieves and work as tanners	s. 60 werden „echte“ Jat mit eigener Sprache (Schmuggler, Händler) und „sogenannte Jat“ beschrieben, die Pashtu sprechen und als Erntehelfer und Worfelkorbmacher arbeiten
	50	CHACHGAR	CHACHGARS make and sell sieves (chaches) and similar household ware	
	128	JOLA	weaver	
	255	PASH	blacksmith	
	168	KULAL	potter	

	348	TRAKAN	carpenter
	30	BATYARAY	frying pan, professional cook
see JIRGA, MARAKA	301	SHARGAR	One who sings or composes songs
see JIRGA, MARAKA, PREKRA	300	SHARAY	improvised poem
	75	DAM	instrumentalist, singer
	167	KUDAY, JADO	sorcery, magic
	76	DAMA	DAMA beautifies the bride on the wedding day and prepares and serves food at the wedding party
	102	DAYGAN	tribe of sharecroppers
	345	TORYAN	dark-skinned nomad people

4.1.5. WOMAN, 29 items				
lists	number dictionary		Atayee	Steul
	304	SHAZA	woman	
see MARAKA	277	RONAY	diaper, infant girl	
	261	PEGHLA	single girl at the age of puberty	
see WEDDING	55	CHURAY	KAKARS word for PEGHLA	
see NANAWATE, PREKRA	196	MAROSHA	married woman	
	199	MATIEZA	any girl who leaves her father's house to search for a husband, girl who elopes with her fiance	
	169	KUNDA	widow	
see NANAWATE	309	SHINGARAY	woman who runs after a man	
	39	BUNDAY	single girl who alleges that someone has tried to assault or assaulted her	
	313	SUR TEKRAY	PEGHLA whose future marriage is claimed by two persons, one of whom is killed by the other; a widow whose husband is killed in enmity	
see LOW SOCIAL STRATUM	76	DAMA	a woman who beautifies the bride on the wedding day and prepares and serves food at the wedding party.	
	205	MINZA	slave woman	

see PASHTUNWALI	9	ARTINA	wife; the adjective for the inferior one	
	211	MOR	mother	
	349	TROR	aunt	
see PASHTUNWALI	326	TARLA	daughter of an uncle	
see PASHTUNWALI	223	NAMUS	chastity, woman	S.140 ff, indirektes und direktes NAMUS
see PASHTUNWALI	248	PARDA	literally „curtain“; to save face	
see PASHTUNWALI	251	PARUNAY	figuratively these words connote woman('s honor/chastity)	
see PASHTUNWALI, WOMAN	329	TEKRAY	figuratively connotes woman	
see NANAWATE, WEDDING	330	TEKRAY AKHISTAL	taking away the shawl of a woman	
	208	MIRAS	inheritance	
see GUILT, NANAWATE, NARKH	212	MORA	married woman who is in love with someone other than her husband	
see JIRGA, MARAKA	305	SHAZA TA LORA WARKAWAL	ceremony of oath taking for a woman	

see MARAKA, MURDER, PREKRA	122	HAD PA HAD KE	the killer side shall give a woman to the heir of the killed one
	314	SWARA	woman given to the heir of the murdered one by the murderer
see NANAWATE	343	TOR SARI	"black-headed", refers to woman
	184	MAKHAIY	a woman given in exchange for another is called MAKHAIY
see WEDDING	293	SPIN PAETSAY	bride married without a wedding party

4.1.6.	WEDDING, 18 items		
lists	number dictionary		Atayee
	352	WADA	wedding
	149	KAWIN	marriage
	116	GHAGWAIL	public announcement by a man that a certain girl will be his future wife

see JAGRA, JIRGA, MARAKA	115	GHAG	„sound, cry“, call the tribe members for help
see NANAWATE	368	ZAGH	in the Eastern dialect ZAGH is GHAG
see NANAWATE	320	TAK KAWAL	to fire a shot from one's rifle, it implies the same concept as TEKRAY AKHISTAL
see NANAWATE, WOMAN	330	TEKRAY AKHISTAL	the taking away of the shawl of a woman
	7	AR	respect
	357	WALWAR	bride-price
see TAWAN	15	BABERAY	increased bride-price
see MARAKA	152	KHALAT	the payment given to the bride's maternal uncle
see MARAKA	191	MANETS	sheep that the son-in-law gives to his mother-in-law three days after the wedding
see GUILT, TAWAN	63	DA ENIGELAI DA SPAKAWALI NAGHA	the fine for insulting a young unmarried girl
	83	DA NAMZADI PA ZOR KOR TA BEWAI	When a future father-in-law does not want to arrange a wedding, the fiance has the right to take away his betrothed from her father's to his own house

		BEWAL	
	89	DA PLAR DA KOR DA NAMZADI DA HAHMADARAI TAWAN	TAWAN for making the betrothed pregnant in her father's house before marriage
	293	SPIN PAETSAY	the bride married without a wedding party
see WOMAN	55	CHURAY	affectionate word for PEGHLA
	111	DRI NIM SARA	an oath given to three male relatives and one female relative of the girl whose engagement to the boy is denied by the family

4.1.7. MULLA, 7 items				
lists	number dictionary		Atayee	Steul
see NANAWATE	216	MULLA	a religious leader	S.92 ff, Ausführungen zum Einfluss der Mullahs
see MARAKA	130	JUMAT	the mosque	
see NANAWATE	268	QURAN	the holy book of Islam	

see MARAKA	154	KHAIRAT	sacrifice and devotion
	53	CHAREY	assistant of the MULLA
see NANAWATE	292	SPIN PATKEY	a title for the MULLA
see MARAKA	51	CHAPA PATA	a very great punishment left over from ancient times; usually a MULLA, will announce the decree

4.2.	CONFLICT / ESCALATION
4.2.1.	GUILT
4.2.2.	MURDER
4.2.3.	JAGRA

4.2.1.		GUILT, 64 items		
lists	Number dictionary		Atayee	Steul
see JIRGA, NANAWATE	340	TOR	accused	
	16	BAD	bad	
see TAWAN	264	POR	literally „debt“; it closely expresses TAWAN; whoever commits an offense is liable to pay a fine	
see TAWAN	246	PAR	someone convicted of a certain crime	
	190	MALAMAT	PAR, anyone proven wrong in a suit	
see NANAWATE	187	MAKHTOREY	any offender or criminal, but in particular an adulterer	
	266	PSHEMANA	penitent and sorry for	
see TAWAN	218	MONKAR	someone denying an act of offense	
	186	MAKHRUNAY	guiltless person	
	252	PAR XRA SPARAWAL	to give someone a donkey ride, to punish a convict	
see NANAWATE,	303	SHARM	"shame", a payment made by the one accused and proven guilty to his opponent	S. 169, 170 Steul zitiert Janata/ Hassas 1975, die

TAWAN, PASHTUNWALI			proven guilty to his opponent	sich wiederum auch auf Kiefer, 1972, beziehen: „Das entschieden wichtigste Regulativ allgemeiner Umgangsformen..’Bescheidenheit, Schüchternheit, Schamhaftigkeit, Schande““, differenziert in ehteram (Ehrfurcht und Zuvorkommenheit gegenüber älteren und höhergestellten Personen sowie dem Gast) und ezat (Höflichkeit und Zuvorkommenheit gegenüber jedem Mann und jeder Frau), Schamgeld
see MURDER, NANAWATE, TAWAN	195	MARG	murder	
see MURDER, NANAWATE, TAWAN	215	MRINA	murder	
see MURDER, NANAWATE	312	SUR-LASSAI	red-handed, murderer	
see MURDER, NANAWATE	351	SUR	red, murder	

NANAWATE				
	270	RABRAYAL	to torture or to torment	
	91	DARAWAL	to threaten	
	36	BLOSAWAL	to incite someone to commit an offense	
	360	WERAWAL	to threaten, to intimidate	
	2	AESAR	the act of challenging a person	
see JIRGA, MARAKA, NANAWATE	287	SPAKA	insult	
	299	SHAR	verbal insult	
	307	SHKANZA	name calling and abusing	
	372	ZERE	swearing, insulting a man by calling names	
see TAWAN	63	DA ENIGELAI DA SPAKAWALI NAGHA	the NAGHA for insulting a young unmarried girl	
see JIRGA, MARAKA	272	RANGA	to disrupt and to destroy	
see MARAKA, TAWAN	77	DA MARAKACHI DA SPAKAWI TAWAN	the TAWAN for disrespecting a MARAKACHI	

	140	KAFAN	„a shroud, a coffin“, a piece of cloth in which the dead corps is wrapped up	
see NANAWATE, PASHTUNWALI, TAWAN	120	HADIRA	the graveyard, the grave	
	175	LARWAHAL	highway robbery	
see TAWAN	310	SHUKA	to rob a traveller of his belonging by force without wounding him	
see TAWAN	178	LOOTAWAL	to plunder	
see TAWAN	52	CHAPAWAL	attack without warning	
	90	DARA	a mass attack without prior notice	
see JUGRA	366	YARGHAL	an attack without a prior notice	
see JUGRA	114	GHADAY	sudden attack at night	
see JUGRA, TAWAN	176	LAS-LAGAWAL	a fight or JUGRA between two or more persons in which firearms or thrust weapons are not used	
	371	ZENA	adultery	

	78	DA MAROSHAY BADALA	the revenge for kidnapping a married woman	
see NANAWATE, NARKH, WOMAN	212	MORA	any married woman who is in love with someone other than her husband	
	143	KARSHANDA	to drag alone, to take someone away by force	
	46	TSAR	to graze, the rope and the nail by which a recalcitrant bull is tied up, to catch	
see TAWAN	80	DA MELMA DA MARG TAWAN	the TAWAN for the killing of a guest	
see TAWAN	73	DA KOR SWAZAWAL	the burning up of someone else's house, hut or KUDAY	
see TAWAN	209	MIRATA	an extreme form of enmity where all of the male members of a family including minors are killed	
	278	SALATA	When no-one is left in a family but an unzealous, coward and unmanly heir, then the family is SALATA.	
	284	SATA	an attack in which all male members of the family or KHEL under attack are killed and houses are put on fire	
	156	KHAY	a total slaughter amongst the Wazieris	
see ORGANISATION OF SOCIAL	22	BALANDARA	collective work, synonymous to ASHAR, its most usual meaning is "joint attack"	

OF SOCIAL LIFE				
see JIRGA, NARKH	37	BRID	attack, assault	
see PASHTUNWALI	347	TRABGANEY	the cut-throat rivalry and enmity among members of the same PLARINA	
	81	DA MIRAS DA PARA QATAL	to kill in order to inherit	
	67	DA KANDAR GHAL	the killing on the spot of a thief entering someone's house to steal	
see JAGRA	374	ZHOBLA	to wound or to injure	
see TAWAN	42	TSALORGORNEY	The TAP by knife, dagger, sword and the like carries fourfold TAWAN.	
see TAWAN	249	PARHAR	injury	
see TAWAN	217	MUNJAY	the one who has a flat nose	
see TAWAN	260	PAZA PREKRA	cutting the nose	
	118	GHOLAY	the surrounding of a house	
	245	PANA	to grant asylum to a guilty or accused person	

	87	DA PALAW GHOTA KAWAL	to tie up a corner of a shawl	
	344	TOR TA DA PANA WARKAWO NETA	the time limit for the refuge given to a TOR	
	297	SHALGUN	a group of people appointed to find and arrest an escaped TOR	
see ORGANISATION OF SOCIAL LIFE	100	DA WACH KHALI AKHISTAL	to take a dried woodchip, a kind of oath-taking in everyday common problems	

4.2.2.		MURDER, 28 items		
lists	number dictionary		Atayee	Steul
see PASHTUNWALI, TAWAN, NANAWATE	17	BADAL	revenge	S. 153, Vergeltung, Rache, Tausch
	281	SARAY	equal	
	185	MAKHAY	equal	
	144	KASHANDA	punishment meted out to a murderer with the agreement of the murderer's relatives	
see TAWAN	79	DA MARI POR PA BADAL KE DA SHAZE DA WARKRE ANDAZA	Literally the number of women given in TAWAN for murder. The purpose of this custom is the reconciliation of the enemies.	
	274	RATAL		
see JIRGA	267	PURA PA PURA		
see JIRGA, MARAKA, NARKH, PASHTUNWALI,	365	WRATA	revenge, retaliation, retribution	

TAWAN			
	40	BUNGA	
see NARKH	158	KHUN	a Persian word which literally means blood; in Pashtun usage it means murder
see GUILT, NANAWATE	215	MRINA	murder and bloodshed
see GUILT, NANAWATE, TAWAN	195	MARG	murder
see GUILT, NANAWATE	312	SUR-LASSAI	red-handed; murderer
see GUILT, NANAWATE	351	SUR	red; murder
see ORGANISATION OF SOCIAL LIFE	101	DA WARMAIG DA WIENI SHARIKWALI	blood relationships
see PASHTUNWALI	362	WINA	blood
	121	HADMATAY	When someone is killed, then the killer side and the father and brother of the killed one are called HADMATAY.

	233	NIK	a cash fine for murder
see PREKRA, TAWAN	285	SAZ WARKAWAL	SAZ like JURA and ROGHA means reconciliation. In the Afridi tribe of Tiera SAZ means the cash payment of TAWAN for a murder
see PREKRA	41	TSALAY	a pillar made of stones loosely put together; the return of SAZ by one getting ready to take revenge
see PREKRA	44	TSALAYWARKAWAL	"the return of SAZ"
	281	SARAY	equal
	185	MAKHAY	an equal one
	144	KASHANDA	a punishment meted out to a murderer with the agreement of the murderer's relatives
see TAWAN	79	DA MARI POR PA BADAL KE DA SHAZE DA WARKRE ANDAZA	the number of women given in TAWAN for murder
	274	RATAL	to expel someone from his tribe
see JIRGA	267	PURA PA PURA	equality or balance

4.2.3.		JAGRA, 13 items		
lists	number dictionary		Atayee	Steul
see JIRGA, MARAKA	124	JAGRA, JUGRA	A serious fight taking place between two groups of people in which bruising, wounding and killing occurs.	
see GUILT, TAWAN	176	LAS-LAGAWAL	a fight or JUGRA between two or more persons in which firearms or thrust weapons are not used	
see ORGANISATION OF SOCIAL LIFE	54	CHIGHA	a call for help, or a call for collective work, usually by drumming	S. 149, „Trommler“, mit dem Trommelschlag wird angezeigt, wenn in der Nähe Schüsse gehört wurden, wenn irgendetwas vorfiel, das den Anschein einer Bedrohung erweckt hat. Cigha wird dann die Versammlung aller waffentragenden Männer genannt, die auf das Schlagen der Trommeln hin oder auf eine Aufforderung anderer Art zusammenstürzt, sofort zum Ort der Tat eilt und die Ursachen der ganzen Aufregung feststellt. Weiterlesen für interessante Fälle, im hinteren Teil Schilderung von Cigha im Einsatz

see ORGANISATION OF SOCIAL LIFE	105	DOL	a double-headed drum
see ORGANISATION OF SOCIAL LIFE	106	DOLCHI	the DOL drummer
see JIRGA, MARAKA, WEDDING	115	GHAG	„sound, cry“
	49	TSWARAY	food in general, in particular it is the food a shepherd takes along with him
see GUILT	366	YARGHAL	an attack without a prior notice
see GUILT	114	GHADAY	sudden attack at night
see ORGANISATION OF SOCIAL LIFE, TAWAN	269	QURAN LOSTAL	to recite the verses of Quran
see PREKRA	355	WALA or WALI	provisional truce
see JIRGA, MARAKA, PASHTUNWALI	119	HAD	bone, in custom it means a member of PLARINA

see PASHTUNWALI, TAWAN	377	ZIERA	beard; symbol of manliness
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4.3.	LEGAL FRAMEWORK / SANCTIONS, PENALTIES, COMPENSATION
4.3.1.	NARKH
4.3.2.	TAWAN

4.3.1.	NARKH, 23 items			
lists	number dictionary		Atayee	Steul
see JIRGA, MARAKA	226	NARKH	tribal customary law	S.223/224, Rechtstradition, die Art, wie Konflikte beigelegt werden und zwar anhand von Analogien zu früheren Beilegungen und Beurteilungen
see JIRGA	337	TOL	weight and to weigh, in the tribal judicial systems it means law	
	321	TALA	weighing scales; it implies justice	
	181	LYAR	tribal law	

see PREKRA	64	DA ESA NARKH	tribal customary law with irreversible decisions	
see JIRGA, MARAKA, PREKRA	56	DA AHMADZO NARKH	a tribal customary law with fixed rules and provisions that attend to the solution of the most complex cases	
	82	DA MUSA NARKH	In MUSA NARKH much attention is paid to BADALA (revenge) in the case of murder.	
	200	MAWADISUNG		
see PASHTUNWALI	256	PASHTO	the language of the Pashtuns; figuratively it connotes truth and reality; the name of Pashtuns tribal law, customs and usages	
see TAWAN	249	PARHAR	injury	
see PASHTUNWALI	289	SPIN	anyone who has not committed an offense or crime	S.54/55, Legende, wie es zu den Begriffen kam, Bezeichnung auch für Clans und Solidaritätsgruppen
see JIRGA, MARAKA	192	MARAKA	tribal customary law court	
see MARAKA	127	JIRGA	A meeting of a group of tribal men that has the authority to settle a dispute in a way acceptable to both sides.	S. 226 (Zusammenfassung) gerichtsähnliche JIRGA bei Konflikten um Eigentums- und Nutzungsrechte sowie zur Beilegung von Konflikten, die die

				Verführung oder Entführung von Frauen betreffen- - befasst sich nur dann mit einem Konfliktfall, wenn noch keine BADAL Handlung erfolgt sind (in der Regel sind dies Tötungshandlungen); s. 229 Jirga als Plattform für Friedensverhandlungen: bei allen schwerwiegenderen Konfliktfällen, die schon zu einer ganzen Reihe von Tötungshandlungen geführt haben
see JIRGA, MARAKA	228	NARKHEYAN	men learned and well experienced in NARKH	
see JIRGA	338	TOLGAR	a member of JIRGA who knows the TOL	
see JIRGA, MARAKA	109	DRI BOJA	threefold, the second increase in the number of NARKHEYAN hearing a certain case	
see PASHTUNWALI, TAWAN	331	TERAY	encroachments on the rights of others	S.216, terai, 1.jede Tötung eines Menschen, ob schuldhaft oder ohne Verschulden,z.B. in einem Unglücksfall 2. jede Körperverletzung (auch der Versuch), d.h. jede dauerhafte und nicht dauerhafte Einschränkung eines

				<p>Individuums in seiner körperlichen Funktionsfähigkeit</p> <p>3. jede Ehrverletzung, d.h. der durch Aktionen oder verbale Äußerungen dokumentierte Zweifel an der moralischen und ethischen Integrität des Individuums oder Gemeinwesens</p> <p>4. jede Handlung (auch der Versuch) gegen die sexuelle Ehre einer Frau, d.h. Annäherung, unsittliches Betragen in ihrer Gegenwart, Verführung und Entführung einer verheirateten Frau-in diesem Fall zusätzlich Verstöße gegen die dem Ehemann ausschließlich zustehenden sexuellen Rechte</p> <p>5. jeder Eingriff (auch der Versuch) in die Verfügungs-, Eigentums- und Nutzungsrechte eines Individuums oder eines Gemeinwesens an einer Sache</p>
see JIRGA, MARAKA, MURDER, PASHTUNWALI, TAWAN	365	WRATA	revenge, retaliation, retribution	
see PASHTUNWALI	16	BAD	literally „bad“; crime, offense	
see PASHTUNWALI	171	LASHKAR	a group of armed men	
see MURDER	158	KHUN	a Persian word which literally means blood; in Pashtun usage it	

			means murder
see MARAKA, NANAWATE	65	DA ISA PA NARKH DA KHUNBAHA ANDAZA	cost of killing
see GUILT, NANAWATE, WOMAN	212	MORA	any married woman who is in love with someone other than her husband

4.3.2.		TAWAN, 55 items		
lists	number dictionary		Atayee	Steul
	328	TAWAN	Literally TAWAN means loss, harm, damage. In tribal customary law it is a payment for POR.	
see GUILT	264	POR	literally „debt“; it closely expresses TAWAN; whoever commits an offense is liable to pay a fine	
see GUILT	246	PAR	someone convicted of a certain crime	
see GUILT	218	MONKAR	MONKAR is the one denying an act of offense. If one confesses that he has committed the offense, the TAWAN may be less than the TAWAN for an offense denied and later proved.	
see MURDER, PASHTUNWALI, NANAWATE	17	BADAL	revenge	S. 153, Vergeltung, Rache, Tausch
	221	NAGHA	NAGHA is a fine levied on an offender.	
	229	NAWAT	NAWAT means compensation for loss; the TAWAN for petty offenses.	
see WEDDING	15	BABERAY	increased bride-price	

see PASHTUNWALI	303	SHARM	SHARM literally means "shame". In tribal customs and usages it is a payment made by PAR (GRAM, MALAMAT), the one accused and proven guilty, to his opponent	S. 169, 170 Steul zitiert Janata/ Hassas 1975, die wiederum sich auch auf Kiefer, 1972, beziehen: „Das entschieden wichtigste Regulativ allgemeiner Umgangsformen...’Bescheidenheit, Schüchternheit, Schamhaftigkeit, Schande“ , differenziert in ehteram (Ehrfurcht und Zuvorkommenheit gegenüber älteren und höhergestellten Personen sowie dem Gast) und ezat (Höflichkeit und Zuvorkommenheit gegenüber jedem Mann und jeder Frau), Schamgeld
	322	TAP	TAP means injury. There are two types: TOR TAP (black injury), which is the injury done to the covered parts of the body such as chest, belly, thighs etc. and SPIN TAP (white injury), which is the injury done to the uncovered parts of the body such as ears, nose, eyes etc.	
see NARKH	249	PARHAR	injury	
see GUILT	42	TSALORGORNEY	The TAP by knife, dagger, sword and the like carries fourfold TAWAN.	

	96	TAP TAWAN	The TAWAN for injury.
	57	DA BADAN DA GHARO TAWAN	According to the ESA NARKH the TAWAN for the mutation and injury of the various parts of the body is determined as follows:
see MURDER, NARKH, MARAKA	365	WRATA	revenge, retaliation, retribution
	38	BUCHA	The cutting of one's nose is BUCHA. When someone cuts another one's nose he must pay TAWAN according to NARKH.
see GUILT	217	MUNJAY	the one who has a flat nose
	260	PAZA PREKRA	PAZA PREKRA means cutting the nose. PAZA PREKRA is categorized as SPIN PARHAR.
	138	KANDASA	The breaking of one's tooth or teeth in a JUGRA is called KANDASA.
	271	RANDAH	RANDAH means blind or to blind someone.
	356	WALJA	WALJA means booty. It is not contrary to the custom to take booty from the enemy.
	164	KOR-SEJAL	KOR-SEJAL means to burn someone's house.
	179	LOTSAWAL	To strip off someone's clothes. It means "to steal", too. If one strips off someone's clothes in order to rob him, the offender has to pay TAWAN. If it is done to insult someone, then SHARM has to be paid

			supplementary to the TAWAN.	
	250	PAR MELMA DA DAZ TAWAN	DAZ means to fire a shot. When someone intentionally shoots someone else's guest without hitting him he is liable to pay the double of the TAWAN of a shot on a non-guest.	
	93	DA SPIN GIEREY GHILA JAZA	The punishment for an old man caught stealing. His beard, mustache and eyebrows are shaved and then publicly scattered. Such punishment is considered the worst in tribal life and the men would prefer to be killed. It is an insult (PEGHOR) to his predecessors.	
see GUILT, NANAWATE, PASHTUNWALI	120	HADIRA	the graveyard, the grave	
NARKH, PASHTUNWALI	331	TERAY	TERAY means encroachments on the rights of others. TERAY KAWUNKI (the encroacher) is PAR and according to tribal customary law has to pay TAWAN. The TAK (land plot) of every member of the tribe is known, encroachment on it is called TERAY. Anyone who makes BELWASA on TAK commits TERAY and is liable to pay TAWAN according to NARKH. The one who commits TERAY is called TERAY KAWUNKI. To be slow in revenging TERAY is a sign of cowardice in tribal morals and ethics. To protect the TAK is everyone's duty.	S.216, terai, 1.jede Tötung eines Menschen, ob schuldhaft oder ohne Verschulden,z.B. in einem Unglücksfall 2. jede Körperverletzung (auch der Versuch), d.h. jede dauerhafte und nicht dauerhafte Einschränkung eines Individuums in seiner körperlichen Funktionsfähigkeit 3. jede Ehrverletzung,d.h. der durch Aktionen oder verbale Äußerungen dokumentierte

				<p>Zweifel an der moralischen und ethischen Integrität des Individuums oder Gemeinwesens</p> <p>4. jede Handlung (auch der Versuch) gegen die sexuelle Ehre einer Frau, d.h. Annäherung, unsittliches Betragen in ihrer Gegenwart, Verführung und Entführung einer verheirateten Frau-in diesem Fall zusätzlich Verstöße gegen die dem Ehemann ausschließlich zustehenden sexuellen Rechte</p> <p>5. jeder Eingriff (auch der Versuch) in die Verfügungs-, Eigentums- und Nutzungsrechte eines Individuums oder eines Gemeinwesens an einer Sache</p>
see GUILT	310	SHUKA	to rob a traveller of his belonging by force without wounding him	
see GUILT	73	DA KOR SWAZAWAL	the burning up of someone else's house, hut or KUDAY	

see GUILT	178	LOOTAWAL	to plunder
see GUILT, JUGRA	176	LAS-LAGAWAL	a fight or JUGRA between two or more persons in which firearms or thrust weapons are not used
see JUGRA, PASHTUNWALI	377	ZIERA	ZIERA literally means beard. The pulling out of a beard in JUGRA has a certain TAWAN if done inadvertently, in case it is done deliberately the TAWAN is fivefold.
	33	BELGA	Anything from among the stolen things found in someone's house
	18	BADAN	An agreement and a pact, usually on forest protection. If anyone cuts down trees, takes away wood or lets his animals graze on the plot of someone else he must pay TAWAN.
	180	LWARA	Taking an oath. False oath has TAWAN.
	288	SPAY	SPAY means dog. Beating, stealing or killing of a dog has TAWAN.
see NANAWATE	364	WRAKA	things stolen or lost
see ORGANISATION OF SOCIAL LIFE	197	MASAPER	A man away from his homeland is called MASAPER. A MASAPER is treated as a guest. The house of a MASAPER is under the protection of the whole tribe with which he lives. If someone damages a MASAPER's door, wall, tent or hamlet, he shall pay "DA MASAPER

			SHARM" supplementary to the TAWAN.
see ORGANISATION OF SOCIAL LIFE	48	TSRAH	It indicates a single toiling man who leaves his home to find employment elsewhere. Since TSRAHS return home with money and valuables, robbing them on their way is not considered an ordinary robbery. The tawan is higher. This is done to safeguard the roads.
see GUILT	52	CHAPAWAL	attack without warning
see GUILT	209	MIRATA	an extreme form of enmity where all of the male members of a family including minors are killed
see GUILT, MURDER, NANAWATE	195	MARG	murder
see GUILT, MURDER, NANAWATE	215	MRINA	murder
see MURDER	79	DA MARI POR PA BADAL KE DA SHAZE DA WARKRE ANDAZA	Literally the number of women given in TAWAN for murder. The purpose of this custom is the reconciliation of the enemies.
see MURDER, TAWAN, PREKRA	285	SAZ WARKAWAL	SAZ like JURA and ROGHA means reconciliation. In the Afridi tribe of Tiera SAZ means the cash payment of TAWAN for a murder

	72	DA KORBA DA SPAKAWI TAWAN PAR MELMA	The TAWAN paid by the guest for disrespecting his host
see GUILT, MARAKA	77	DA MARAKACHI DA SPAKAWI TAWAN	the TAWAN for disrespecting a MARAKACHI
see GUILT	80	DA MELMA DA MARG TAWAN	the TAWAN for the killing of a guest
	58	DA BADRAGAY DA MAKH NEWAY TAWAN	It means the TAWAN to be paid for holding up the way of BADRAGA
	94	DA SPI TAWAN	The TAWAN of a dog.
	222	NAGOONA	NAGOONA is the limit of the TAWAN for GHILA (theft).
see GUILT	63	DA ENIGELAI DA SPAKAWALI NAGHA	the NAGHA for insulting a young unmarried girl
	97	DA TOPAK NAGHA	A fine to pay for disrespecting the rifle
see JAGRA, ORGANISATION OF SOCIAL LIFE	269	QURAN LOSTAL	to recite the verses of Quran

4.4.	JUDICIARY & LEGISLATIVE FUNCTIONS AND FORA
4.4.1.	MARAKA
4.4.2.	JIRGA

4.4.1.MARAKA, 75 ITEMS					
	lists	number dictionar y		Atayee	Steul
	FRAMEWORK FOR MARAKA				
	see JIRGA, NARKH	192	MARAKA	tribal customary law court	
	see JIRGA	127	JIRGA	Meeting convened to investigate and settle tribal matters	S. 226 ff, S. 229 ff
		31	BAWAR	Trust	

	see JIRGA	363	WISA	Trust
		27	BARAMTA	pledge
		182	MACHALGA	surety
	see JIRGA	353	WAK	the consent to accept the MARAKA'S decree as irrevocable
		193	MARAKA- CHEYAN	member of MARAKA
	see MULLA	130	JUMAT	mosque
	see JIRGA, ORGANI- SATION IN VILLAGES	24	BANDA	temporary dwelling outside the KALA, a place where MARAKA and JIRGA are held
	see JIRGA	376	ZIARAT	graveyard of a tribe's ancestors
	see PASHTUN- WALI, JIRGA	235	NIKA	grandfather
	LAW			

	see JIRGA, NARKH	226	NARKH	tribal customary law	S.223/224, Rechtstradition, die Art, wie Konflikte beigelegt werden und zwar anhand von Analogien zu früheren Beilegungen und Beurteilungen
	see JIRGA, NARKH, PREKRA	56	DA AHMADZO NARKH		
		3	AHMADZAI POR		
	PEOPLE				
	see JIRGA, ORGANI- SATION OF SOCIAL LIFE	198	MASHAR	respected title	Janata, 1973: „der Ältere“, S.100, Steul, „Informeller Führer, dessen Einfluss auf Gemeinschaftsentsch eidungen unbegrenzt sein kann und dessen Autorität nicht in einem von der Gemeinschaft übertragenen Bereich limitiert und festgelegt

					ist.(...) Oberhaupt einer fraternal joint family.“ S. 101:“Männer, die sich einen Ruf als ghairatman erworben haben.“
	see JIRGA, ORGANISATION OF SOCIAL LIFE	282	SARKHEL	MASHAR	
	see JIRGA, ORGANISATION OF SOCIAL LIFE	206	MIR	tribal MASHAR	
	see JIRGA, NARKH	228	NARKHEYAN	men well experienced in NARKH	
	see JIRGA, NARKH	109	DRI BOJA	threefold, the second increase in the number of NARKHEYAN hearing a certain case	

	see JIRGA, WOMAN	305	SHAZAY TA LORA WARKAWAL	a woman taking oath
	REASONS			
	see JIRGA, JUGRA	124	JAGRA, JUGRA	serious fight
	see GUILT, JIRGA, NANAWATE	287	SPAKA	insult
	see JIRGA, JUGRA, PASHTU NWALI	119	HAD	bone, member of PLARINA
	SETTLEMENT			
	see JIRGA, PREKRA	129	JURA	truce, reconciliation

	see JIRGA, PREKRA	276	ROGHA	truce, reconciliation	S. 225, „rugha“, Frieden, Gesundheit
	see PREKRA	234	NEKA	truce, reconciliation	
	see PREKRA	265	PREKRA	settlement	
	see PREKRA	161	KHWLA MATAWAL	announcement of PREKRA	
	see JIRGA, PREKRA	332	TIGA	stone, truce	S. 225, „tigha“, Stein „Wird ein Konflikt schließlich in einer JIRGA beigelegt, so wird ein kleiner Steinhaufen aufgeschichtet, nur wenige Zentimeter hoch, und von einer der Führungspersönliche iten umgestoßen als Zeichen dafür, ‚dass kein Stein mehr zwischen Euch ist‘.
		23	BAND	prevention	
		26	BANDUN		

	see PASHTUN- WALI, JIRGA, PREKRA	123	HOD	decision, resolution
	see MURDER, PREKRA, WOMAN	122	HAD PA HAD KE	ROGHA, reconciliation through giving a woman
	see WOMAN	277	RONAY	newborn girl
	EXPENSES			
	see JIRGA, ORGANI- SATION OF SOCIAL LIFE	308	SHLAWAND	the act of determining the shares
	see ORGANI- SATION OF SOCIAL LIFE, PASHTUNWA LI	194	MARAY	meal
	see WEDDING	152	KHALAT	gift given to MARAKACHEYAN, payment given to the bride's maternal uncle

	see MARAKA, ORGANI- SATION OF SOCIAL LIFE	336	TOIGH	expenses of MARAKA
	see JIRGA, MULLA	53	CHAREY	assistant of the MULLA
		146	KATAOW- GARZAWAL	The act of collecting money for the gifts to MARAKACHEYAN considering a big national problem
	see JIRGA	298	SHANDANA	special payment for the expenses of MARAKA or JIRGA
	see JAGRA, JIRGA, WEDDING	115	GHAG	sound, cry
	OATH			
		241	OWA SARA PREKAWAL	taking oath
		283	SAR PREKAWAL	taking oath
		95	DA TAIGH LWARA	taking an oath with a blade
		294	SPIN SARUNA	unbiased people are called to take an oath and reveal the truth

			SARUNA	
	DISCUSSION			
	see NARKH	188	MAL	friend, comrade-in-arms, a partner and an assistant
	see JIRGA	323	TAPI	seasons
	see JIRGA, NANAWATE	172	LAMAN	skirt, excuse, forgiving and granting refuge
	see JIRGA, MURDER, NARKH, PASHTUN- WALI, TAWAN	365	WRATA	revenge, retaliation, retribution
	see MULLA	51	CHAPA PATA	to break down all tribal relations with the offender
	see NANAWATE, NARKH	65	DA ISA PA NARKH DA KHUNBAHA ANDAZA	The cost of KHUN (killing)

	MEDIATION			
		110	DRIMAN	third ones
	see JIRGA	204	MEYANZ- GARAY	mediator
	see JIRGA	4	AILCHI	middleman
		69	DA KATAWI PAKHAWAL	Cooking meals for the mediator
	see JIRGA	341	TORA AW SPINA	black and white
	CELEBRATION			
	see WEDDING	191	MANETS	the PASA that the son-in-law gives to his mother-in-law three days after the wedding, a PASA killed for the celebration of a successful MARAKA
	see PASHTUN- WALI	259	PATKAY	turban
		19	BADANA	robe of honor
	see JIRGA, LOW	301	SHARGAR	

	SOCIAL STRATUM			
	see JIRGA, PREKRA, LOW SOCIAL STRATUM	300	SHARAY	improvised poem
	see MULLA	154	KHAIRAT	sacrifice, devotion
	NOT SATISFIED			
		227	NARINA	generous, courageous, hospitable...
	see PREKRA	131	KAGA	prejudiced PREKRA
		62	DA DABARO TAKAWAL	striking two stones against each other
	see JIRGA	132	KAGA KHABARA	disruptive words
	see GUILT, TAWAN	77	DA MARAKACHI DA SPAKAWI	the TAWAN for disrespecting a MARAKACHI

			TAWAN	
	see JIRGA, PREKRA	66	DA KAGAY GHAG	announcing dissatisfaction with PREKRA
	see GUILT, JIRGA	272	RANGA	to disrupt, to destroy
	ZADRAN TRIBE			
	see MARAKA, PREKRA	295	SPIN ZADRAN	The Zadrán tribe belongs to SPIN GUND and that is why Zadrán is called SPIN ZADRAN.
	see PREKRA	112	DWA WIESHT SAGA	respected place, seat of SPIN Zadrán MARAKA
	see JIRGA	125	JAMA	JAMA is a MARAKA to bring about reconciliation
		319	TAKHAM	appeal to a second MARAKA

4.4.2.	JIRGA, 44 items
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lists	number dictionar		Atayee	Steul
see MARAKA	127	JIRGA	A meeting of a group of tribal men that has the authority to settle a dispute in a way acceptable to both sides.	S. 226 (Zusammenfassung) gerichtsähnliche JIRGA bei Konflikten um Eigentums- und Nutzungsrechte sowie zur Beilegung von Konflikten, die die Verführung oder Entführung von Frauen betreffen- - befasst sich nur dann mit einem Konfliktfall, wenn noch keine BADAL Handlung erfolgt sind (in der Regel sind dies Tötungshandlungen); s. 229 Jirga als Plattform für Friedensverhandlungen: bei allen schwerwiegenderen Konfliktfällen, die schon zu einer ganzen Reihe von Tötungshandlungen

				geführt haben
see MARAKA, NARKH	192	MARAKA	tribal customary law court	
	99	DA TORE BAIRAGHONO JIRGA	JIRGA convened under the black flags	
see MARAKA, NARKH, PREKRA	56	DA AHMADZO NARKH	The Ahmadzao Narkh has fixed rules and provisions that attend to the solution of the most complex cases.	
see MARAKA	363	WISA	Trust	
see MARAKA	353	WAK		
see MARAKA	125	JAMA	a MARAKA to bring about reconciliation	
see MARAKA, NARKH	226	NARKH	tribal customary law	S.223/224, Rechtstradition, die Art, wie Konflikte beigelegt werden und zwar anhand von Analogien zu früheren Beilegungen und Beurteilungen
	337	TOL	weight and to weigh, in the tribal judicial systems it means law	

see MARAKA, NARKH	228	NARKHEYAN	men learned and well experienced in NARKH	
see NARKH	338	TOLGAR	a member of JIRGA who knows the TOL	
see MARAKA, NARKH	109	DRI BOJA	threefold, the second increase in the number of NARKHEYAN hearing a certain case	
see MARAKA, ORGANISATION OF SOCIAL LIFE	282	SARKHEL	Kochi word for MASHAR and MIR	
see MARAKA, ORGANISATION OF SOCIAL LIFE	206	MIR	a tribal MASHAR	
see MARAKA, ORGANISATION OF SOCIAL LIFE	198	MASHAR	a respected title given to one by his tribe	Janata, 1973: „der Ältere“, S.100, Steul, „Informeller Führer, dessen Einfluss auf Gemeinschaftsentscheidungen unbegrenzt sein kann und dessen Autorität nicht in einem von der Gemeinschaft übertragenen Bereich limitiert und festgelegt ist.(...) Oberhaupt einer fraternal joint

				family.“ S. 101:“Männer, die sich einen Ruf als ghairatman erworben haben.“
see MARAKA, MURDER, NARKH, PASHTUNWALI, TAWAN	365	WRATA	revenge, retaliation, retribution	
see MURDER	267	PURA PA PURA	equality or balance	
see GUILT, NANAWATE	340	TOR	accused	
see MARAKA	4	AILCHI	middleman	
see MARAKA	204	MEYANZGARAY	a mediator between two persons or two tribes	
	68	DA KATAWI PAKHAWAL	cooking meals for the mediator	
see MARAKA	341	TORA AW SPINA	Black and white	
see MARAKA	298	SHANDANA	special payment for the expenses of MARAKA or JIRGA	

see MARAKA, PREKRA	265	PREKRA	settlement	
see MARAKA, PREKRA	276	ROGHA	reconciliation	
see MARAKA, PREKRA	129	JURA	truce and reconciliation	
see MARAKA, PREKRA	234	NEKA	JURA and ROGHA	
see MARAKA, PREKRA	332	TIGA	stone, truce	
see MARAKA	132	KAGA KHABARA	disruptive words uttered in MARAKA or JIRGA	
	333	TIGA MATAWUNKAY	"The stone breaker", the one who breaches the provisions of TIGA.	
see GUILT, MARAKA	272	RANGA	to disrupt, to destroy	
see MARAKA, PREKRA	66	DA KAGAY GHAG	announcing dissatisfaction with the PREKRA of a MARAKA or JIRGA	
	227	NARINA	generous, courageous, hospitable	
see MARAKA	376	ZIARAT	graveyard of a tribe's ancestors	

see MARAKA, PASHTUNWALI	235	NIKA	grandfather	
see MARAKA, ORGANISATION IN VILLAGES	24	BANDA	a temporary dwelling outside the fortified village	
see JAGRA, MARAKA	124	JAGRA	A serious fight taking place between two groups of people in which bruising, wounding and killing occurs.	
see MARAKA	323	TAPI	seasons, the occurrence date of the event under discussion	
see GUILT, MARAKA, NANAWATE	287	SPAKA	insult	
see MARAKA, PASHTUNWALI, PREKRA	123	HOD	decision and resolution	
see JUGRA, MARAKA, PASHTUNWALI	119	HAD	bone, in custom it means a member of PLARINA	
see GUILT, NARKH	37	BRID	attack, assault	

	104	DODAY	bread, MELMASTEYA (entertainment of guests), expenses of JIRGA	
see JAGRA, MARAKA, WEDDING	115	GHAG	„sound, cry“	
see MARAKA, MULLA	53	CHAREY	assistant of the MULLA	
see MARAKA, ORGANISATION OF SOCIAL LIFE	308	SHLAWAND	the act of determining shares	
see MARAKA, ORGANISATION OF SOCIAL LIFE	336	TOIGH	expenses of MARAKA or JIRGA, contributing to the living expenses of someone	
see MARAKA, NANAWATE	172	LAMAN	skirt, in customs it means excuse, forgiving and granting refuge	
see MARAKA, LOW SOCIAL STRATUM	301	SHARGAR	someone who sings or composes songs	

see MARAKA, PREKRA, LOW SOCIAL STRATUM	300	SHARAY	improvised poem	
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4.5.	RECONCILIATION (PROCESS)
4.5.1.	NANAWATE
4.5.2.	PREKRA

4.5.1.	NANAWATE, 44 ITEMS			
lists	number dictionary		ATAYEE	STEUL
	224	NANAWATE	ceremony of pardon-begging	S. 143,144 Steul beschränkt sich auf Teilbedeutung des Begriffes im Zusammenhang mit Asylbitte und übersetzt in diesem Sinne „Schutz und Hilfe für Schwache“; Zitat Caroe, 1965: “The denial of sanctuary is impossible for one who would observe Pakhtu, it cannot be refused even to an enemy who makes an approach according to nanawati-a

				verbal noun carrying the meaning of ‚coming in‘. This is an extension of the idea of Melmastia, hospitality, in an extreme form, stepped up to the highest degree.“
	29	BASHAL	pardon	
see MURDER, PASHTUNWALI, TAWAN	17	BADAL	revenge	Steul zitiert Janata Hassas 1975 : „Tausch, Ersatz, Kompensation, Äquivalent, Rückgabe, Vergeltung“
	60	DABARA	stone	
	65	DA ISA PA NARKH DA KHUNBAHA ANDAZA	cost of killing	
	72	DA KORBA DA SPAKAWI TAWAN PAR MELMA	TAWAN for disrespecting host	
	84	DA NANAWATE TARTIEB	the arrangement of NANAWATE	
see JIRGA, ORGANISATION	104	DODAY	bread	

OF SOCIAL LIFE, PASHTUNWALI				
	140	KAFAN	shroud, coffin	
see GUILT	187	MAKHTORAY	offender, criminal, adulterer	
see GUILT, MURDER, TAWAN	195	MARG	murder	
see GUILT, MURDER, TAWAN	215	MRINA	bloodshed, murder	
see PASHTUNWALI	253	PASA	sheep	
see GUILT, MURDER	312	SUR-LASSAI	red-handed, murderer	
see GUILT, MURDER	351	SUR	red, murder	
see PASHTUNWALI	177	LOKHAY	sheep given in NANAWATE	
	285	SAZ WARKAWAL	reconciliation	
see JIRGA, MARAKA	287	SPAKA	insult	
	299	SHAR	verbal insult	

see GUILT, NANAWATE, PASHTUNWALI, TAWAN	303	SHARM	shame, payment	S. 169, 170 Steul zitiert Janata/ Hassas 1975, die wiederum sich auch auf Kiefer, 1972, beziehen: „Das entschieden wichtigste Regulativ allgemeiner Umgangsformen...’ Bescheidenheit, Schüchternheit, Schamhaftigkeit, Schande“, differenziert in ehteram (Ehrfurcht und Zuvorkommenheit gegenüber älteren und höhergestellten Personen sowie dem Gast) und ezat (Höflichkeit und Zuvorkommenheit gegenüber jedem Mann und jeder Frau), Schamgeld
see GUILT, JIRGA	340	TOR	accused	
see TAWAN	364	WRAKA	things stolen or lost	
see GUILT	371	ZENA	adultery	
	372	ZERE	swearing	
	172	LAMAN	(skirt), excuse, forgiving, granting refuge	

	216	MULLA	religious leader	
see MULLA	268	QURAN	holy book of Islam	
see MULLA	292	SPIN PATKEY	title for the MULLA	
see PASHTUNWALI	296	STANA	the God-favored and holy	
see WEDDING	320	TAK KAWAL	to fire a shot from one's rifle	
see WEDDING, WOMAN	330	TEKRAY AKHISTAL	taking away of the shawl of a woman	
see WEDDING	368	ZAGH	woman proclaiming a man her husband	
see PREKRA, WOMAN	196	MAROSHA	married woman	
see WOMAN	212	MORA	any married woman who is in love with someone other than her husband	
see WOMAN	309	SHINGARAY	woman who runs after a man	
see WOMAN	343	TOR SARI		
see ORGANISATION	214	MRAYAY	slave	

OF LIFE				
	170	LAGHAR PIRAN	a tribe in Khost	
	70	DA KAT PSHA NEWAL	holding the leg of the CAT	
	258	PA QABAR KE CAMLASTAL	lying down in the grave	
	244	PALAW	pardon begging by a woman	
	247	PARAY PA GARA ACHAWAL	pardon begging by putting a rope around the neck	
	354	WAKHA PA KHWLA KE NEWAL	customary ceremony in order to beg forgiveness	
see GUILT, PASHTUNWALI, TAWAN	120	HADIRA	graveyard, grave	

4.5.2. PREKRA, 31 items				
lists	number dictionary		Atayee	Steul
see JIRGA, MARAKA	265	PREKRA	settlement	
see JIRGA, MARAKA	129	JURA	truce, reconciliation	
see JIRGA, MARAKA	276	ROGHA	reconciliation	S.223 rugha=Gesundheit
	285	SAZ WARKAWAL	reconciliation	
see MURDER	41	TSALAY	pillar of stones, return of SAZ	
see JAGRA	355	WALA or WALI	provisional truce	
see JIRGA, MARAKA	332	TIGA	stone, truce honored by both sides	
see MARAKA	234	NEKA	JURA, ROGHA, reconciliation	S.223, rugha=Gesundheit
see NANAWATE	60	DABARA	stone, truce	
	327	TARUN	pact or treaty, temporarily or permanently	

see PASHTUNWALI, MARAKA, JIRGA	123	HOD	decision, resolution	
see MARAKA	112	DWA WIESHT SAGA	seat of SPIN ZADRAN MARAKA	
	85	DA NETE TIEGA	temporary truce	
see MARAKA, MURDER, WOMAN	122	HAD PA HAD KE	reconciliation for murder by giving a woman	
	43	TSALAY-RANGAWAL	"removing the tombstone", reconciliation after killing of men	
	174	LANGAR	food as well as the place where food is served for visitors by sacred people who collect charity	
see JIRGA, MARAKA, LOW SOCIAL STRATUM	300	SHARAY	improvised poem	
	88	DA PAR BARAMTA	see BARAMTA (27, list MARAKA), pledge	
	367	YARGHAMAL	to give someone in guarantee	
	370	ZAMINGARAY	persons given as pledge in provisional truce	
	70	DA KHABAR TIEGA	time and notice TIEGA	

		TIEGA		
see MARAKA	161	KHWLA MATAWAL	„to break one's mouth“, the announcement of PREKRA	
see JIRGA, MARAKA, NARKH	56	DA AHMADZO NARKH	a tribal customary law with fixed rules and provisions that attend to the solution of the most complex cases	
see NARKH	64	DA ESA NARKH	tribal customary law with irreversible decisions	
see MARAKA	295	SPIN ZADRAN	tribe with a very precise MARAKA and an irreversible PREKRA	
see JIRGA, MARAKA	66	DA KAGAY GHAG	announcing dissatisfaction with the PREKRA of a MARAKA or JIRGA	
	162	KOG-NARKH	PREKRA in favor of one side contrary to the rules of NARKH	
see MARAKA	131	KAGA	prejudiced PREKRA	
	311	SHUMA NEWAL	the refusal to eat with someone in order to bring about ROGHA	
	173	LA MARAI NA LASSLEWAL	see SHUMA NEWAL	

4.6. STEUL

List Steul	
Pagenumber in Steul	
preface, p.XIV	Die Werte des Paschtunwali werden heute im Widerstand gelebt. Es bleibt zu hoffen, dass sie irgendwann einmal auch wieder in einem Afghanistan gelebt werden, das selbst über sein politisches Schicksal bestimmen kann.
p. 34, 1.2.1.1. Einfluss der Clan- und Lineageorganisation im sozialen Bereich	Beispiele für verschieden begründete Solidaritätsansprüche, s. 38 Zitat Sprichwort: „May God give a man cousins against his enemies, brothers against his cousins, and sons against his brothers.“ (mitgeteilt und übersetzt: Prof.El Ham, 26.4.1077)
p.54, 1.2.4. Die spin und tor Paschtunen	Versuch einer Erklärung des Ursprungs und der Bedeutung im Sozialen
p. 56 1.2.5.1. Die Hindus/Sikhs, S. 60 1.2.5.2. Die Jat	Nochmal Hintergrund für Eigenbild der Paschtunen, was „Besseres“ zu sein
p.88, 2.2.1.3. Kontrolle der Wasserverteilung	Erklärung der Aufgaben des kacai/mir-ab (Wasserkontrolleur), kommt bei Atayee nicht vor. Im Becken von Khost nötig, da viele Blutfehden auf Grund von „Wasserklau“ entstehen.
p. 101, 2.2.2.42 „haji“	Wird bei Atayee nicht erwähnt. Steul zitiert JANATA über Einfluss der Männer, die die haj gemacht haben.
p. 102, 2.2.2.5. Religiöse Führer	Beschreibung der und Auflistung von Saids in der Region. Zitat.“ Ein Paschtune ist (damit) a priori Besitzer der Wahrheit und der Said muss beweisen, dass er sie in größerem Maße besitzt. Vorher und nachher Zitat von Ahmed, 1076, über social significance of the religious belief (unilineal descent from Abdur Raschid)
p.111, Politische Allianzen	Fallbeispiele für Funktionieren von Allianzen
p.146, humsaya	Asyl-Befohlener, aber auch landloser Abhängiger (ersterer kann zu letzterem werden), der kein freier Paschtune sein kann
p.151, tura, „das Prestige des	Kommt so bei Atayee nicht vor, „ Heldenmut,

Einzelnen“	Mannestum, Tapferkeit“, bei (turalai= Held), bei nang/nangialai= auf den Schutz anderer ausgerichtet, tura auf die Verteidigung eigener Interessen gerichtet
p.153 3.1.2.1.	Zitat: Wie betont, geht der Paschtune davon aus, dass er ständig bedroht ist. ...Der einzelne Paschtune hat sicher keinen Anlass zur Paranoia, wohl aber zur Vorsicht.
p.160, unter 3.1.2.1. Badal	Zitiert Ahmed, dass die badal-Forderung das Aufkommen und Überleben von Gewalttätern unmöglich mache. Selbst ein aggressiver Mann könne keinen Terror ausüben und mit Gewalt Besitz und Macht akkumulieren. Es würde immer zu einem nanawati und dem Eingehen von humsaya-Verhältnissen kommen. Der Bedrohte würde sich einen Beschützer mit einer mindestens ebenso großen Solidaritätsgruppe suchen.
p. 160/161 salem	nicht bei Atayee, als salem wird jemand bezeichnet, der über das als Badal tolerierte Maß an „Ausgleichsgewalt“ hinausgeht. Zwar gibt es keine festgelegten Regeln, was oder wieviel den Ausgleich herstellt, aber die Gemeinschaft hat das „im Gefühl“, und wer mehr macht, ist nicht mehr turalai, sondern salem und wird nur in Maßen toleriert. Schlägt er extrem darüber hinaus, wird von der Gemeinschaft gewaltsam gegen ihn vorgegangen. Dafür hat Steul konkrete Beispiele.
p.177 3.2., Die Postulate der paschtunischen Gesellschaft im Becken von Khost	<p>Postulat 1:</p> <p>Der Paschtune ist souverän. Mit Ausnahme der Patriarchen hat niemand das Recht, ihn in seiner Handlungs- und Entscheidungsfreiheit einzuschränken.</p> <p>Postulat 2:</p> <p>Das Gemeinwesen ist souverän. Niemand hat das Recht, eine Familie, eine Lineage, einen Clan, eine politische Allianz oder ein Dorf in ihrer Handlungs- und Entscheidungsfreiheit einzuschränken.</p> <p>Postulat 3:</p> <p>Das Leben ist hart, die Welt ist feindlich.</p>

	<p>Individuum und Gemeinwesen sind ständiger Bedrohung ausgesetzt und müssen sich souverän verteidigen.</p> <p>Postulat 4:</p> <p>Das Individuum ist dem Gemeinwesen verpflichtet und umgekehrt. Individuum und Gemeinwesen sind zu gegenseitiger Solidarität verpflichtet, wobei die Interessen des Gemeinwesens den Interessen des Individuums gleichgestellt sind.</p> <p>Postulat 5:</p> <p>Eigentum an Land ist die Garantie der Existenz und der Souveränität, für Gemeinwesen und Individuen.</p> <p>Postulat 6:</p> <p>Frauen, Garanten des Fortbestandes der Paschtunen, sind Männern im Wert nachgeordnet.</p> <p>Da Frauen physisch schwächer und zudem moralisch anfälliger sind, müssen sie vor physischen Angriffen und moralischer Anfechtung geschützt werden. Sexualität ist ausschließlich in der Ehe gestattet, die sexuellen Rechte stehen ausschließlich dem Ehemann zu.</p>
p.203 zetah	<p>nicht bei Atayee, „Stengel (einer Pflanze), Stamm“, d.h. in der Übertragung auf Mord an einem Familienmitglied, dessen Land einem dann im Erbe zufällt; man hat eine Gewalttat gegen die eigene Existenzgrundlage begangen, verstößt gegen die Solidaritätsforderungen gegenüber der engsten Familie, vergeht sich am Stengel einer Pflanze, deren Teil man selber ist.“</p>
p.225, 3.3.2.3. dawa, tigha	<p>dawa (nicht bei Atayee)=Normbruch</p> <p>Im Falle eines dawa sind die Parteien verfeindet, im Sprachgebrauch heißt es, dass ein Stein (tigha) zwischen den Parteien liegt. Wird ein Konflikt schließlich in einer jirga beigelegt, so wird ein kleiner Steinhäufen aufgeschichtet, nur wenige Zentimeter hoch, und von einer der</p>

	<p>Führungspersönlichkeiten umgestoßen als Zeichen dafür , „dass kein Stein mehr zwischen euch ist“. Fußnote zalai= Steinhaufen/Monument- mit dem Zusammenlegen mehrerer Steine wird auch am Ende einer jirga mit legislativem Charakter symbolisiert, dass ein Beschluss gefasst wurde, der eine Norm setzt, z.B. die Festlegung eines Verbotes und eines nagha.</p>
<p>p.233, 3.3.2.3.3., nek- Kompensation am Beispiel der Tani Nek= Wiedergutmachung</p>	<p>Steul erklärt hier die <i>nek</i> Zahlungen für die Verletzung verschiedener Körperteile. Atayee nennt <i>nik</i> nur als cash fine for murder. Das, was bei Steul und den Tani nek- Zahlungen sind, wird bei Atayee <i>tawan</i> genannt.</p>

5. CONCEPTUAL FRAMING OF THE UNDERLYING STRUCTURE

5.1. MAPPING THE NORM-SANCTION COMPLEX

According to Atayee, *Pashtunwali* comprises “all the customs, traditions, heritage, customary law and usages and all social relations, the concept conveying the socio-economic political and cultural system in totality.” He is thus in line with the proponents of a comprehensive, all-encompassing definition of its contents, such as Elphinstone, Sigrist, Janata/Hassas, Spain, Steul, and Glatzer. For instance, Steul (p.308) posits that “*Pashtunwali* is comprised of the sum of the total values and social norms which determine the way of life peculiar to the Pashtuns. It is the all-embracing regulator for the preservation and conservation of the society and for the behavior patterns of the individual. It is an emic concept which includes everything which a Pashtun should or should not do. It is thus a means of ethnic identification and differentiation in relation to other ethnic groups.” Elphinstone gives many detailed examples of how these behavior patterns influence the relation between the tribes and the existence or rather non-existence of any central government. It is intriguing that these same patterns can be clearly seen in today’s political and societal situation.²²

Although *Pashtunwali* is present in all the Pashtun tribes, according to both Atayee and Spain it is most adhered to among the free tribes of the Sulaiman Mountains on both sides of the Durand Line.

²² A detailed analysis of Elphinstone’s observations compared to current conditions will be prepared by the author as soon as possible.

Pazhwak states that the term *pashtu* itself is not only the name of the language, but denotes a purpose in life and is used as a synonym for the term *pashtunwali* that is better known in the Western countries.

In line with Durkheimian terminology it would not be far-fetched to classify *Pashtunwali* as a *fait social total* which permeates tribal Pashtun society in defining norms and sanctions. While norms can be defined as socially expected, respectable and aspired-to behavior, they are invariably linked to their respective antitheses, i.e. any infringement or violation of norms. Sanctions are designed to counter any trespassing beyond the more or less precisely defined demarcation lines of boundaries of tolerable (mis)behavior. Under *Pashtunwali*, the defined norms and sanctions for social demeanor and interactions are valid for individual and group levels. Obeying and abiding by *Pashtunwali* regulates interactions within Pashtun tribal society in that what is acceptable and what is not, as well as the to-be-expected but also to-be-exacted respective penalties are clearly defined. Thus, an equilibrium is created ensuring a minimum of societal balance.

The threshold to intra- as well as inter-group violence at the sub-tribal level can be considered very low across the Pashtun tribal belt. However, there are slight differences among the various areas of southern Afghanistan and north-western Pakistan, especially with regard to penalty structure and conceptual terminology. What exists as a specific term in a given area does not necessarily need to exist under the same term and/or in the same socio-legal conceptual manifestation (i.e., exhibiting the exact same structural or content-related properties) in other areas. Material collated by Steul is mentioned next to Atayee's definitions in the

annex wherever there is terminological overlap, so that the scope of differences and differentiation can be compared. ²³

Among Pashtun tribesmen only very few would be in a position to lay out the structure of the system, including the relation, interconnectedness and dynamics between the various notional clusters or conceptual components in a systematic manner. However, while the term *Pashtunwali* is not known by all tribal Pashtuns, the basic tenets are manifest throughout the Pashtun crescent and there are a number of essential commonalities between regional variations of the code of honor. These shared characteristics revolve around the key pillars of honorable behavior and are thus all linked to the norm sanction complex. This said, the differences in the various manifestations abound in the specific details of the legal aspects of *Pashtunwali* (contained in the *narkh* complex), including the code of penalties, reparations, and compensation for moral harm suffered or physical injuries endured (*nek, tawan*).

As a rough overview, one can say that the *Pashtunwali's* most important tenets are all directly or indirectly linked to the norm sanction complex in that they represent various concepts all at least partially related to the notion of individual and/or group honor(-ability). The concepts in question are *pashto* (wholesomeness), *ghairat* (respectability), *sharm* (decency, pudor, shame), *namus* (honorability), *nang* (honor), *tura* (valor, boldness), and *melmapalana* (hospitality); thus, various shades of the key quality of "honor". All are to be

²³ Steul collected his data in the basin of Khost during various visits to Afghanistan which he carried out between 1972 and 1977. Atayee was a "cultural official" in Helmand, Kandahar, Nangarhar and Paktiya. He collected material on the *Pashtunwali* that different researchers had worked on for several years. He then authenticated them by discussing them with elders of authority, mainly in the plains of the Sulaiman Mountains, Baluchistan/Pakistan. His dictionary was published in 1979.

understood as state or condition, and performative qualities. These interlocking concepts all share the characteristic of a bipolarity in that they are on the one hand performative act(ion)s and on the other, represent a condition or state of possessing honorable attributes or qualities.

Hence, all these notions refer both to properties possessed by an individual and, by extrapolation, the concentric circles of different group levels the individual belongs to, from the household over *khel* (sub-clan/settlement unit) all the way to *kam* (clan) and tribal meta-unit (or vice versa, collective action reflecting on the individual)²⁴, as well as to performing (doing) honorable acts and displaying positively-sanctioned qualities to thereby restore, maintain or increase one's honorable reputation and self-worth. Performing a certain act which covers the aspect of displaying/showing a specific quality or attribute to the surrounding environment connects the realms of doing and having the specific honorable quality. In the closely-knit communities where reputation is everything and even the slightest suspicion or "lingering odor" potentially tainting one's reputation is sanctionable by (tribal) law, the moral pressure of societal expectations is omnipresent in that it governs what is permissible and what is not.

The duality of the norm sanction complex is exemplified by the fact that infringements against one's honor—passively suffered or received—carry the obligation to restore the individual, family, clan, or tribal respectability via codified negative sanctions (which are to be "meted out", as put by Atayee's translator). The latter, by being performed, are thereby also publicly displayed in real time

²⁴ Group solidarity is of the essence in feuding and non-compliance with the customary expression of alliance is heavily sanctioned. For instance, there are substantial penalties for village or clan members not answering to the call of the (village) drums signaling an emergency (attack against the village, call to arms to form a retaliatory posse or expedition etc.).

(or, by word of mouth, with a slight delay). Beneficial effects on one's individual or group reputation can be derived from righting a wrong done upon oneself or one's group as well as by ostentatious display of social standards of respectability that are commonly positively sanctioned, such as a high degree of hospitality (*melmapalana*). Positive and negative sanctions are functions of (peer) group pressure. The latter is built on expectations fuelled and underscored by the "rules" laid down in the customary code of social regulation and behavior. The enforcement of sanctions to compensate for an actual or perceived wrong as well as the conspicuous display of generosity through *melmapalana* are thus eminently social acts in the Weberian sense in that they are to a large extent directed toward the surrounding community of fellow group members who know how to interpret the deeds or signals through the shared code of norms. Thus, the seemingly innocuous display of hospitality can have a substantial side of playing to the audience in the way of what must be understood as conspicuous consumption similar to potlatch logic. Here, elements of cousin rivalry (*tarborwali*) come into play, triggering the counter-dynamic of status envy (*siyali*).²⁵

On a conflict curve, the above concepts can all be categorized as typical triggers of retaliation to right a perceived or factual wrong. As far as the facticity of a wrong and thus the justifiability and social acceptance, indeed: expectation and (peer) pressure of a negative sanction is concerned, there is not much difference between a concrete deed and the mere perception of the latter. Redeeming one's honor after having suffered a wrong/norm violation (*terai*) is no longer optional if the potential misdeed is perceived as such by even a restricted public (peer group, clan etc.). The important factor when it comes to exacting revenge is that retaliatory action will often lead to the social and moral obligation of the

²⁵ Steul quotes a Pashtun saying which stipulates "May God give a man cousins against his enemies, brothers against his cousins, and sons against his brothers."

adversary to take revenge, which not seldom then results in a spiral of violence which at least during the initial stages is often still socially accepted, if not even openly expected and endorsed, in line with the concepts of *nangialai* and *turalai*. There is also an inbuilt control of non-endorsed excessive reactions which leads to dissuasive peer pressure to put an end to the spiral of violence or not even start it if the issue is considered too trivial or wanton provocation is involved (*salem*). This regulator draws a line between *badal* covered under *narkh* and *tura*, and actions not socially endorsed, separating morally acceptable braveness and fearlessness in the face of adversity (*tura*) from random challenges leading to unnecessary violence and loss of life. Following the principle of an eye-for-eye (*pura pa pura*), the *tawan* (penalty) of *badal* (blood revenge) can easily result in a back and forth of retaliatory feuding until finally the community pressure on both sides as well as the internal motivation inside the feuding camps will have subsided and the reconciliation procedures according to the institutionalized process of *nanawate* come into play and a *jirga* or *maraka* is called. The hierarchical relations and sequential differentials between the various concepts can be framed as shown in the following tabular overview:

Function / Process	Term		General Concept
Reconciliation (institution, process)	<i>prekra; jura; rogha</i>		<i>nanawate; pura pa pura</i>
	<i>maraka; jirga</i>		
Sanction	<i>badal</i>	<i>tawan (nek etc.) / jugra</i>	<i>por; narkh (salem not covered by ~)</i>
Triggers linked to norms / conflict catalysts (perceived and/or factual transgression or encroachment)	<i>zan (sharm!)</i>	<i>zamin (tarbor!)</i>	<i>namus / sharm (zan and zamin specifically linked to reproduction / defensive resources)</i>
	<i>sar (namus)</i>		
	<i>wrata; khun etc. (murder / homicide); sharm; tarburwali; siyali</i>		<i>terai (violation of norms) resulting in badal (“mechanical” character of sanction/if-then dynamics; peer pressure); tarborwali; siyali (optional reaction)</i>
Core value(s) (leitmotif/ideal)	<i>ghairat; to have/to do pashtu (ehteram, ehtazab, melmastya / melmapalana etc.)</i>		<i>ghairatman; nangialai (nang); turialai (tura)</i>
Framework of norms and values regulating social life	<i>pashtunwali</i>		social stratification; organization of social life including structure of settlements/housing; overall social framework regulating social interaction

5.2. FROM ZAN, ZAR, ZAMIN TO SAR; ZAN & ZAMIN - DISCUSSING STEUL'S "POSTULATE"

The Persian alliteration "*zan, zar, zamin*" (literally: woman, gold, land) is often referred to as formula capturing the driving forces behind Pashtun society. Indeed, in the literature this triad of "desirable resources" is portrayed as triggering most of the violent conflicts. However, when exposing the formula to a reality test it becomes clear that the autochthonous rural population is not familiar with this concept. Steul, in questioning the validity of this conflict formula points out that among his Pashtun informants, not a single one had ever heard of *zan, zar, zamin*, nor its corresponding Pashtun translation. The endogenous Pashtun conflict formula put forward by the natives was "*mar, khadza, msaka*", which translates into death, woman, land. Hence, there is overlap in that woman and land are also part of it. However, the Persian alliteration mentions woman in first position, arguably due to the flow of the alliteration (*zar, zan, zamin* or any other combination is by comparison clearly lacking in elegance, from a phonological point of view). Most noteworthy is the fact that the emic definition replaces "gold" (the Persian "*zar*") with "head" (the Pashtun "*mar*") as reference to physical and moral integrity, which intriguingly not only captures visible damage to one's body but also violations of the psychological sphere, i.e. the invisible integrity of one's honor.

In line with the above, Steul thus suggested nearly three decades ago to forget about the less accurate non-Pashtun version of *zan, zar, zamin* to have it replaced in the academic literature by the conflict formula used by tribal Pashtuns themselves. As a concession to the flow of the Persian language as opposed to the much harsher Pashtun (not to mention the even more rustic dialectic variety of Pakhto) he suggested the alliterative Persianized version of the Pashtun

sequence *mar, khadza, msaka*; namely: “*sar, zan, zamin*”. This formula was to place the reference to physical as well as psychological integrity (Pashtun *mar*, Persian *sar*) in first position. Thus, the reference to a person’s or community’s “head” and by implication, the violation of body and/or mind, was to replace the notion of material possessions (*zar*/gold) given that the latter play(ed) a comparatively minor role in reality as well as rural Pashtuns’ self-perception.²⁶

Since all the major concepts related to triggering *terai, badal* under *narkh* fuelled by *nang* and/or *tura* are either related to damages of physical and/or moral integrity, the emic conflict formula (and Steul’s corresponding Farsi version) make perfect sense in that they accurately reflect reality rather than bending it to the linguistic convenience of outside observers. In an attempt to further conceptualize the Pashtun conflict formula “*sar, zan, zamin*”, Steul went ahead to code the totality of 114 concrete, empirical conflicts that had occurred in the Khost valley according to his informants. The “theses” (German: “Postulate”) he derived from this analysis can be grouped as follows:

²⁶ This revised formula has been steadfastly ignored in the literature, probably due to the fact that he presented his research findings in German and not in English, which made them less accessible on the international stage.

Formulaic reference/ “code”	Thesis / Postulat following Steul’s sequence; item no. 6 (“subordinate”) is listed here prior to item no. 5 (“land”) in line with “coding”	Key Notion
sar	1. Uphold your individual and your affiliation group’s honor // <i>turalai</i> 2. Uphold your tribe’s honor // <i>nangialai</i> 3. The world is hostile // “be ready to defend your life as well as your reputation’s integrity at any given moment”	Readiness to re-establish and rehabilitate one’s, or one’s group’s, physical integrity and/or reputation
zan	4. Uphold women’s/your wife’s honor // <i>sharm, namus, ghairat</i> 6. Woman, reproductive basis of (Pashtun) society, is subordinate to man.	Readiness to defend individual and group’s reproductive resources
zamin	5. Uphold your control over land // <i>sharm, namus</i>	

The above mapping exercise makes it clear that the concept of *sar* indeed overrides the two others in that *sharm, namus, ghairat*, which are integral concepts of the definition of *zan* and *zamin*, are all inherently linked to the notion of maintaining or restoring physical and/or mental integrity. A more refined model able to better capture the underlying architecture of the Pashtunwali’s normative logic would place Steul’s third thesis (“the world is hostile, be ready to defend yourself and your kin”) in the first position.

Steul	Refined Logic
1. <i>turalai</i>	I-III hostile world
2. <i>nangialai</i>	Ia <i>turalai</i>
3. hostile world	Ib <i>nangialai</i>
4. women's honor	IIa women's honor
5. control of land	IIb women subordinate
6. women subordinate	III control of land

Also, rather than modelling the theses in linear sequential logic, a spatial representation would allow for capturing content overlap and inclusiveness.²⁷ Consequentially, the following model is suggested:

²⁷ Steul's items 4 and 6 are lumped together, here, since both refer to man's obligation to defend female group members.

5.3. CRACKING THE CODE – DECYPHERING THE PASHTUNWALI'S FUNCTIONAL UTILITY

A specific society's set of norms and values can be seen as structure regulating societal upkeep. This structure provides orientation and a basic philosophy or worldview (*Weltanschauung*) which in turn generates a sense of stability. Historic, economic, and cultural factors (as well as geographical and climatic factors linked to the previous three) all have a more or less pronounced influence on the specific manifestation and articulation of a society's psychological mindset. The previous chapters have dealt with the descriptive analysis of this particular normative structure, its apparent logic and its hidden articulation. What emanates from the preparatory descriptive groundwork and the subsequent step of searching for the internal architecture behind those norms and values and related sanctions is the intriguing question about the root cause of *Pashtunwali's* tenets. Accordingly, this sub-chapter attempts to pinpoint key tenets underlying the functional utility of this specific code of ethics.

How did historical, cultural, socio-economic and geographical factors shape slightly different manifestations of the same set of values (informing sets and sub-sets of norms and sanctions of *Pashtunwali*) which are shared throughout the Pashtun crescent? Looking at the set of basic options that are open to any society is helpful, here (1). And so is looking into the structure of Pashtun society (2). We will briefly delineate basic patterns to be found in Pashtun society and then combine them for analytical purposes.

(1) There are three basic types of possible behavior individuals, groups, or societies can exhibit vis-à-vis the surrounding environment. These range from (a)

the predisposition for outward-going, extroverted exchange, trade, cooperation over (b) a more introverted tendency to withdraw and shy away from contact or submissiveness resulting in mimicking the example of more powerful outside groups to (c) displaying an assertive self-containedness which might manifest itself in either aggressive combativeness or a more passive, defensive resolution to stick to one's own ground. No single group will over the course of history display among all its individual members only one of the above profiles and often all three elements are intertwined and more or less pronounced among society and in its dealings with its surrounding environment. In the case of tribal Pashtuns, however, the third characteristic clearly stands out.

The impenetrable rugged hill-side terrain and harsh weather conditions made it difficult for outside conquering forces to subdue the Pashtuns. For one, their physical prowess predisposes them to physical, agricultural labor and martial abilities. Historical coincidence might have placed them in an exacting environment of severe climatic conditions or their specific cultural and economic skills set might have made them move into the specific environment they inhabit nowadays. On the other hand, the natural environment will have also had at least a certain impact on the collective characteristics and typical mentality²⁸ but further impacted upon by ruthless natural selection via centuries of sub-alpine agriculture in trying weather conditions. The influx of the sturdiest Alexandrian troops who survived the conqueror's advance till its farthest advance to Northern India added to the genetic pool and might have had a bolstering effect, as will have the probable further conditioning of their fighting abilities through the battle-hardened, experienced Macedonian troops. Pashtuns would not only specialize in agriculture but also in the art of warfare, with the occasional looting of Silk Route caravans. Pashtun troops were a sought-after brand of mercenaries who

²⁸ Again, it needs to be stressed that any given group will never represent but one type of character but that one can often find typical traits shared by the majority of group members, or commonly shared referential qualities, or behavioral properties typically exhibited by such group members.

would fight for the highest bidder, and especially Persian kings often hired their talented fighters. On the other hand, Pashtuns also invaded and ransacked neighboring kingdoms (the ransacking of Delhi by Pashtun troops occupies a prominent place in their collective memory).

(2) Pashtun society is non-hierarchical and segmentary. Pashtun society's structure is acephalous, meaning there is no standing authority or centralized government. Institutions such as tribal councils or armies are established on a flexible by-need basis, i.e. only if and when required by circumstances. Each and every single male individual has the same rights and entitlements, at least in the collective consciousness. The male individual is his own sovereign although respect and deference is required vis-à-vis elders and fellow peers even in the case of gaping differences in economic fortune (*ehteram, ehtezab*) and religious honorables (*sayed, pir, mullah*). Non-religious leadership positions (*khan, malek*) can in theory be seized by any individual provided he can muster the allegiance of his peers to instate him in such a rank. The leader among men cannot rest on his laurels but, given his innate status of *primus inter pares*, is constantly potentially challenged by members of his clientele or in-group. The selective mechanisms and principles of Pashtun society are inherently merit-based. Hence, any (male) individual blessed with exceptional rhetorical, managerial and/or martial skills can make his way into a leadership position. At the same time, alertness against rivalling peers comes with a premium. The equality in ranking among individuals is magnified toward higher levels of demographic integration, to the sub-clan, clan and sub-tribal levels. Any given group is by definition equal to its peer segments, i.e. sub-tribe. "A" has by definition the same standing as sub-tribe "B". There is a binary logic to the segmentary logic which implies that any given segment, down to the household level, has an antagonist within the specific in-group, and beyond it (*siyali, tarborwali, tor-gund* divide etc.). Rivalry and status competition is a key defining element within as well as between the elements of the segments.

That individual and group level manifestations of the concept of honor enshrined in *Pashtunwali* are closely interrelated in the tightly-knit community structure of rural Pashtun society was shown earlier. What transpires from the analysis of Atayee's and Steul's empirical data and research into segmentary societies are the following core components and characteristics of the tribal Pashtuns' psycho-social mental complex:

- The rural Pashtun tribesman is socialized as "*Wehrbauer*" (German for peasant-warrior) fiercely determined to defend his individual and collective soil, reproductive resources and honor;
- Infighting and alliance shifting is commonplace, but formerly competing segments can just as easily join forces to fight a common enemy;
- There is a certain paranoid character permeating Pashtun rural society that, figuratively speaking, constantly keeps everybody "on his toes" ready to defend himself as well as ready to pounce, expecting incursions upon his integrity or honor at any time;
- There is a marked divide between rural, traditionally oriented Pashtuns and urban Pashtuns (the Ibn Khaldunian analysis of the "decadent elites in the ivory tower" is very helpful indeed in providing a theoretical framework for this insight; it needs to be mentioned here that non-Pashtun provinces share similar antipathies against the stifling tendencies of the central government vis-à-vis its provincial counterparts);
- Collective paranoia is further spurred by the inherent competitive predisposition, especially of young Pashtun males who still have to prove themselves as *turalalai* and by extension aspire to establish a reputation as *nangialai*, resulting in a constantly volatile equilibrium that can skip into dynamic instability typically governed and thereby regulated by the conflict curve *terai/badal-tawan-narkh/nanawate*;

- The driving forces of cousin rivalry (*tarborwali*) and status envy (*siyali*) go a long way in explaining outbursts of seemingly random or chaotic violence;
- The closely interrelated factors of individual and group reputation built on respectability and honor(ability) are the overriding, most precious commodities which, on the grounds of their esoteric, non-physical character, are potentially assailable at any time.

The norm-sanction complex based on Pashtunwali's inherent values harbors an important element of deterrence which constitutes an integral part of the system's logic. *Nang, tura, namus, siyali, tarborwali* and the related predicated violence curve as well as very low violence threshold not only constitute an intricate system of social conventions of how violence is regulated and channelled, but at the same time functions as a deterrent against the trespassing of rules and norms and thus, as control and prevention of violence. In short, the norm-sanction complex represents (customary) law. Sanction x leads to the predictable sanction y, and this spanning across up to seven generations, if need be. This results in the maintenance of defensive qualities as well as a system of conflict regulation.²⁹ While this system is archaic in the sense of *pura-pa-pura/eye-for-an-eye* and the extremely low threshold of violence and an exacerbated complex of male pride and honor, there is no lawlessness. To the contrary, the socio-geographical playing field of tribal interactions is regulated by an omnipresent set of intricately interrelated "invisible vectors" governed by *Pashtunwali's* elements.

²⁹ Just as the looming specter of capital punishment will not (always) prevent capital crimes in modern, industrialized Western societies, violent deeds fuelled by passion, aspiration, and emotions (for instance in the process of performing *gakh*, or reacting to it) are not always prevented. This, however, cannot be held against customary law which has its own mechanisms of regulatory justice (not only blood feud, but also *tawan, nek* under *narkh*). To boot, *badal* is not only peters out after two or three rounds of retaliatory action when reputations of *tura/nang* are re-established and the head count is even, but is also controlled by *salem*.

Predictable penalties and sanctions work like a collective insurance policy. The latent levels of violence in the interest of upkeeping peace are artfully linked with the maintenance of collective defensive as well as offensive military potential. On a collective scale, the forces articulated and upkeep in chronic internal strife, can amalgamate and rise to acute collective forces when a challenge manifests itself at the collective level. Conjuring up these forces is presently considered by Western military strategists who consider a repetition of the approach implemented during the Iraqi surge. What is apparently not considered, however, are the counterproductive effects which are of mechanical predictability since the Pashtuns do by no means share a collective enemy as was historically the case in the jihad against the Communist PDPA regime and their Soviet supporters. To the contrary, in the present situation, Pashtun tribal support is divided between the central regime, anti-governmental forces (al Quaeda, Taliban, Gulbuddin Hekmatyar etc.) and neutral onlookers, fence-sitters and opportunistic swing voters.³⁰

The political landscape is almost as ragged as the hilly geography, with such diverse players as traditional khans, mujahideen warlords, neo-clientelistic networks of poppy industry strongmen, politico-religious brokers and entrepreneurs, posses of professional mercenaries, with frequent cases of ragtag overlaps or spurious alliances between most of the above. Providing additional resources (cash, money, political access) to select “allies” does not take into account the inherent volatility of the segmentary pyramid, its binary logic and key elements of cousin rivalry and status envy. Freeing the genie from its bottle might

³⁰ Under the present security situation, the veracity of any political survey in the tribal areas about the political affiliation or support to the government is at best heavily skewed by fear of (violent) repression and sanctions of the various alliances of political players, at worst completely useless.

over the middle to long run result in yet another unforeseeable phenomenon such as the historical rise of the Taliban. The following chapters will present a critical reading of how the dynamics on the ground are currently playing out and, by inference, how they could further develop if a “surge” approach was naïvely followed, before looking into more realistic, viable alternative pathways that would allow for sustainable development in the tribal areas.

6. READING THE CURRENT SITUATION THROUGH THE “EMIC, ETHNICO-TRIBAL PRISM”

6.1. WEIGHING THE EFFECTS AND CONSEQUENCES OF MISJUDGMENT

In the following specific terms of Atayee’s dictionary are presented in their full length and followed by examples how the underlying rules of pashtunwali are related to current crucial events.

The presented concepts have implications on, for instance, the issue of Afghanizing the military effort by bolstering ANA troop levels in the South, the debate about a potential increase of foreign troop presence or the chances for negotiations with the Taliban and how to frame them.

17 BADAL

Whatever is paid for TAWAN (compensation) is BADAL. Whoever commits an offense is liable to pay BADAL. It may be levied on the offender by MARAKA or JIRGA(tribal customary law court) or the offended person may take his own BADAL. The BADAL (literally meaning: revenge) for killing is to kill, but this may be amended through NANAWATE (ceremony of pardon-begging) and JIRGA. The one who does not take his BADAL is considered a coward. Mount Stuart Elphinstone, an English researcher and political officer who traveled through some Pashtun tribal areas in the beginning of the 19th century, writes in "The Kingdom of Kabul" that according to Pashtunwali everyone has the duty and the right to take his BADAL. Despite government propaganda against BADAL it has become part of the code of the tribal law. A person may wait a long time to take BADAL. For a Pashtun it is PEGHOR (shame, negation of manliness) not to take BADAL. In some tribes the family will take BADAL and sometimes the whole tribe will help to take BADAL. BADAL can be avoided through reconciliation by NANAWATE.

331 TERAY

TERAY means encroachments on the rights of others. TERAY KAWUNKI (the encroacher) is PAR (guilty) and according to tribal customary law has to pay TAWAN (compensation). The TAK (land plot) of every member of the tribe is known, encroachment on it is called TERAY.(...) To be slow in revenging TERAY is a sign of cowardice in tribal morals and ethics. To protect the TAK is everyone's duty.

- Operation Enduring Freedom (OEF) started in late 2001; rapidly, the defeat of the Taliban and al Qaeda was announced. OEF continued to do the “cleaning up”. More than eight years later the insurgents have regrouped and are stronger than ever before, confident enough that in late 2006 they announced a large scale offensive for 2007 designed to take over large parts of southern Afghanistan. By mid-2009, the Taliban are upbeat and asking the US President as well as other Western governments to unilaterally withdraw their troops, while the new US administration declared Afghanistan the primary war theater and is allocating tremendous resources to its related war effort and introducing a number of aggressive managerial changes, revamping and overhauling the entire military set-up, mechanisms, strategic approach and key staffing positions. Death tolls among civilians are continuously on the rise. So are casualties among Western troops, as well as the insurgents’ side. The result is not increased security for the civilians and improved quality of life, but to the contrary increased terror and insecurity in large parts of the south, as well as in other regions of Afghanistan.
- Denouncing that insurgents and al Qaeda operatives are hiding behind civilians does not justify killing civilians in the process of engaging enemy combatants. After eight years of this practice, US Defense Secretary Robert Gates and other top military officials said in early 2009 that reducing civilian

casualties would be crucial. Meanwhile, air-strikes were still being conducted on civilian entities.^[1] Even after U.S. Gen. Stanley McChrystal changed the guidelines and battlefield rules in July in order to reduce the civilian casualties the air strike executed on September 4th in Kunduz claimed many innocent victims. The German Bundeswehr might have even been lured into a trap set up by the Taliban by ordering the air strike support. Can we rule out the possibility that the fuel trucks got maneuvered there on purpose? Whatever the outcome is, the Taliban win: Civilian victims killed by Western bombs will indirectly contribute to their standing and if there is no bombing, they will just continue their war.

In addition, given the long number of years that certain tribal areas have effectively been a war theater, with no sign of the insurgency waning, civilians might be pushed in the direction of the lesser evil: if facing a choice between increased exposure to bombardment over an intolerably long time with no concrete hope of the insurgency ever being subdued, against having to live under the insurgents' rule.

- The longer the insurgency is not showing signs of losing in strength, the higher the risk of increasing frustration levels among Western and ANA troops. The more the fighting drags on and the higher the intensity levels of the conflict, the higher the numbers of seized suspects and subsequent interrogations. Higher frustration levels lead to higher risks of resorting to illegal practices such as psychological and potentially even physical torture applied against suspects (insurgents, collaborators, informants, spies etc.).³¹ An increasing number of

³¹ Embedded journalists have reported that beatings and torture are being practiced in the ANA and OEF efforts directed against insurgents and suspected collaborators (Wolfgang Bauer and Karsten Schöne; "Operation Folter—Die Kämpfe in Afghanistan werden immer brutaler. Amerikanische und einheimische Soldaten quälen und prügeln bei Verhören" (page 86-92); FOCUS, 25.6.2007).

tortured or ill-treated suspects heightens the risk of producing an ever-larger number of innocent individuals who, as a reaction to the ill-treatment they were subjected to, are more likely to turn against the anti-insurgent effort and actively side with the insurgents.³²

- It has been reported that prisoners transferred to the Afghan security service “National Department of Security” by ISAF, have been mistreated and tortured.³³ While torture as such is banned by international treaties it is in addition bound to produce new Taliban recruits in those cases where the suspects are innocent and turn against the government as a result of being mistreated. President Obama’s executive order signed in January 2009 to close the Guantanamo Bay detention facility within a year is a step in the right direction. However, it will not suffice as long as there remain doubts whether Afghan government forces have indeed stopped the alleged practice of torturing.
- By committing ever more troops to the military confrontation the Western alliance is going down the path of a de facto-occupation of the southern part of Afghanistan. This not only further alienates the local population, since more troops will foreseeably result in more fighting leading to more civilian casualties, but also lessens support for the current government and its Western assistance. When speculating about a needed commitment of several decades of Western military presence in Afghanistan what is not clear is whether anybody has factored in the threshold of tolerance to having to live in

³² The Red Army followed a policy of incentives and reprisals in dealing with the Afghan rural population to make them cut ties with the insurgency. However, the latter only strengthened the resolve of the insurgents and resulted in antagonizing the previously uncommitted, producing an additional number of very determined insurgents (those who had witnessed or survived reprisals, or had lost family members during punishments meted out at the collective level).

³³ Die Tageszeitung; July 30, 2007, p.10.

a war theater. The effects are incalculable, ranging from large-scale demographic shifts (which, as recent migrations to Kabul indicate, have picked up in speed and overall dimensions, in 2008) to the (remaining) population's majority teaming up with the insurgency thereby creating an even more hostile setting for ANA and Western troops.³⁴

- Military strategic wisdom (Clausewitz) holds that war is the continuation of politics with other means. This also applies to “asymmetrical warfare” implies that a war should never be waged in a fashion and with a mindset that makes it impossible to talk to the opponent, go back to the negotiation table and reach a truce and finally, a peace agreement.
- Waging a war designed to annihilate the opponent (as exemplified by the “Hammer and Anvil” code name of the initial military campaign set up to catch the insurgents between American forces pushing from the northern side and Pakistani military awaiting them on the southern side of the Durand line, in 2002/3) not only severely limits the available options but also results in self-vilification and auto-denigration and is thus ultimately not only inefficient but counter-productive, esp. if many of the opponents one is fighting obey a cultural code of honor that asks them to take revenge at any cost, sooner or later (there is a Pashtu saying “a Pashtu took revenge after one hundred years and still was in a hurry” (Atayee, *BADAL*). Western politicians and military strategists need to understand that for every tribesman killed the Western alliance is not contributing to lasting peace but instead pouring fuel into the

³⁴ Costs at the collective psychological level including everybody living in the southern war theaters (be it actively or passively involved) are just one factor among other costs habitually ignored when analyzing the impact of fighting (pollution of the countryside, effects on wildlife, the potential dissemination of mines by insurgents resulting in future suffering etc.).

confrontation increasing it in scale and intensity, as well as sowing the seeds for future generations of anti-Western as well as anti-Western backed Afghan government fighters and suicide bombers.

101 DA WARMAIG DA WIENI SHARIKWALI

The "common neck blood", i.e. the blood relationships. All those belonging to the same PLARINA (the unit of a tribe that has a common ancestral father) are considered blood relatives. If a member of a PLARINA commits murder, all PLARINA are considered enemies by the murdered side. Anyone of DA WARMAIG DA WIENI SHARIKWALI may be killed by the side of the murdered in GHACH (revenge).

225 NANG

NANG / NANGA in tribal customs means to guard the courage, grace and generosity and other good qualities of Pashtunwali. NANGA is the central point of PASHTUNWALI. All good qualities are based on the principles of NANGA. "Nanga kawal" means "to protect one's right". "Da warore nanga kawal" and "Da kam nanga kawak" mean "to defend the rights of one's brother" (to defend the rights of one's tribe). All those who die in the way of NANGA are not forgotten. Such people become legendary figures.

- On the scene of the battle, young Pashtun fighters will likely compete to try to outdo the others by showing what mettle they are made of. On the one hand the individual is in constant competition with the others driven by the principle of cousin rivalry. Secondly, individual acts of bravery or boldness reflect on and build the honor of the family and lineage the individual belongs to. This

makes for an element of unpredictability that created many problems for the Russian Army's military planners.³⁵

- Should the leader of a group of insurgent Pashtun fighters get killed, all other fighters are there to fill his position, and most of them do indeed have the leadership skills needed to lead men on the battlefield since their customary code of conflict regulation is based on principles of measured, codified retaliation following the principles of “an eye for an eye” and survival of the fittest. (Mentally and physically handicapped people are often hidden away in villages because of shame, if they are not slowly starved into illness and ensuing death during childhood. At the same time the Taliban movement's leadership was and almost certainly still has one of the physically most crippled leadership there is in the world (many lost limbs on the battlefield due to mortars, bullets, and mines.) Killing the military leader of a Taliban group will not automatically result in the group taking off and trying to rescue themselves. They might retreat and evade aerial bombing, but then only to decide upon a new leader. Killing all the leaders would not necessarily result in the military structure losing its drive. Every Pashtun fighting as a free man considers himself intrinsically equal to his leader. He is only tolerated, accepted and followed as long as his special qualities that made him a leader or rather tolerated *primus inter pares* in the first place, are continuously demonstrated.³⁶ Losing these qualities (or getting killed) will result in the

³⁵ See the account of former SAS mujahideen trainer Tom Carew (*Jihad!-The Secret War in Afghanistan*; 2000).

³⁶ This logic is cruel but also efficient in its selection of individuals with superior fighting skills. Parallels to highly competitive social set-ups like star-studded sports teams but also the animal kingdom are evident; successful and long-lasting leaders who are accepted, tolerated, supported by their followers or team members are normally alpha individuals with superior specialized skills in the strategic and organizational as well as technical area who build their status on earned respect from others of whom potentially many if not all others are vying for the top spot and challenge the established authority at

immediate re-orientation of the former followers, who then decide upon a new leader. In a war of attrition the Taliban would not lose in fighting determination and arguably not in fighting quality since their segmentary society has a self-replicating socio-psychological as well as cultural code that leads to the reproduction of military leadership potential on an unprecedented scale. What made the Pashtuns fighting against the Russian Army so successful was that whenever the leader was shot in direct combat, the Pashtun fighting contingents would not be head-less, but in fact multi-headed, with the top leader's gap immediately being filled.

365 WRATA

WRATA means "revenge, retaliation, retribution". In the case of murder, the heirs of the killed have the right of WRATA. Not to take WRATA is the indication of cowardice. In common usage WRATA is the TAP TAWAN (compensation, eye for eye, tooth for tooth and so on). To determine WRATA exactly is the duty of MARAKA and JIRGA (tribal customary law court); however, limits and standards of WRATA are laid down in customs and NARKH (tribal customary law). In a case for which WRATA is not known in NARKH, the MARAKA or JIRGA has to determine the WRATA. Such WRATA serves as a precedent. If the JIRGA does not know that there is a precedent for the WRATA in the case under hearing and fixes a different WRATA, then the one sentenced can remind the JIRGA of the precedent and the JIRGA has to listen to him.

the first signs of weakness. This selection mechanism of course tends to promote only the toughest and most able individuals, in the first place. Leadership training and selection in modern armies is not different in that new leaders are not in short supply, with the difference that in the division of labor and linked to the specialization of tasks and roles and the related separate training, the circulation of leaders often leads to individuals without first-hand battle experience taking over. The spells of duty that are limited to a certain time period result in experienced but, due to psychological reasons, also mentally the most worn-out soldiers rotating out of the duty station after a certain number of months, whereas the Taliban are not known to rotate their staff out of duty on a grand scale (however, it is by now clear that the Taliban have an R&R cycle that allows them to replenish their spirit and forces away from the frontline, every now and then. These R&R periods are apparently normally being spent either in Uruzgan, Peshawar, Quetta, or the respective hometown of the Taliban fighter if it is a local Pashtu).

316 SIYALI

SIYAL means rival and SIYALI is rivalry. To have equal prestige with a SIYAL is very important in tribal life and is an indication of zeal and pride. TARBRONA (cousins, relatives of the same tribal branch) are the SIYALAN of each other. In SIYALI every SIYAL tries not to trail behind the tail of his SIYAL. Neighbors are SIYAL in hospitality. SIYALI means to be better in every aspect of life than the SIYAL.

225 NANGA

In tribal customs it means to guard the courage, grace and generosity and other good qualities of Pashtunwali. NANGA is the central point of PASHTUNWALI. All good qualities are based on the principles of NANGA. "Nanga kawal" means "to protect one's right". "Da warore nanga kawal" and "Da kam nanga kawak " mean "to defend the rights of ones brother" (to defend the rights of ones tribe). All those who die in the way of NANGA are not forgotten. Such people become legendary figures.

350 TURA

TURA means sword. Figuratively it means courage. Turzan is courageous. Possessing TURA means being courageous and a warrior. TURA is sacred and disrespect for it makes one liable to pay NAGHA. One swears by TURA. If someone is engaged to a girl and is away from home his family can get the girl married to a TURA as with TOPAK (rifle). After the ceremony of such a marriage the family of her husband takes the girl along. She lives there until her husband returns. When someone does a courageous act for guarding the grace of the tribe, he is called "turaiwakra" (he did Tura). The cover of TURA is called teki. There is a Pashto command saying: "Don't take TURA out of its teki, but if you do, then get it red" (with blood).

- Stocking up ANA troops would require massive enlistment of both Pashtun and non-Pashtun soldiers. Sending Pashtun ANA soldiers into the battle zone carries the risk of Pashtun alienation and creating or deepening intra- as well as inter-ethnic divide. By sending mainly or exclusively non-Pashtun fighters, the idea of a common multi-ethnic Afghanistan with a shared identity might be

jeopardized. Fomenting intra-Pashtun tensions would be risked by triggering the dynamics if not “mechanics” (automaticism; predictable consequences) of *wrata* and *badal* linked to *tura* and *nang*, all of which are further fuelled by *siyali* and *tarborwali*.

- By the same token, the idea of a repeat of the Iraqi Surge, i.e. having some tribal Pashtuns fight against other Pashtuns siding with or actually being part of, the Taliban (or al Qaeda) is likely to lead to intra-tribal mayhem and blood revenge, furthering the weakening of both pro-government as well as pro-insurrectionist tribal clans. The Taliban are masters in manipulating and “playing” the patronage and client systems permeating southern Afghan (Pashtun) power politics. Brute combined Western/ANA force and centrally organized politics might be a recipe for upkeep of a semblance of control but not for effective governance, nor the sympathy of the people. Rather, it is a recipe for losing the battle over hearts and minds. The longer the fighting continues, the higher the likelihood that support for the Western-backed Karzai-regime will slip away.
- The tribal Pashtun areas in north-western Pakistan (in the FATA and the NWFP) are by no means in all areas actual “terrorist safe havens”. First of all, the emic perspective of who is a terrorist is arguably diametrically opposed to the self-portrayal of the Western forces. Secondly, insurgents are not helped everywhere, in fact, they are facing purges by local tribes in some, but again by no means all areas. And this seemingly contradictory and illogical pattern does not seem all that surprising when reading the situation through an historically informed socio-anthropological perspective. The Taliban movement, essentially Pashtun by composition, is only one player in a complex web of social interaction mainly driven by what can be qualified as an instable equilibrium or stable instability of social alliances in the face of constant threats and security

challenges which are not at all new to the area nor its inhabitants. This is the very reason why their stringent code of values and ethics which constitutes the basic foundation of the social code of regulation, forms the law of the Pashtun heartland. As in any corpus of law, the underlying principles cannot readily be formulated by any given individual/member of the Pashtun tribe but the do's and don'ts or positive and normative norms and sanctions are very much alive and kicking in all areas where functioning tribal communities are in place. A given breach of a norm will be sanctioned, usually by violence, which deters transgressions at any given moment. At the same time, the concepts of *turalai*, *siyali* and *tarborwali* act as countervailing forces keeping everybody on his toes against the onslaught of potential violence from outside.

- The insurgents' confidence level is boosted as they interpret the increased momentum of their insurgency as tipping the overall balance in their favor. For them, a stalemate already foreshadows victory, which points at an important strategic asymmetry vis-à-vis the government and Western forces. While the government and the West are fighting for complete control of the territory, they cannot be content with a stalemate: The insurgents have a strategic advantage in that they have time and geography, and the tradition of ultimately successful resistance against super-powers (Britain in the days of the Raj, then later the Soviet Union) on their side. The historical memory of the veteran anti-Soviet fighters is that when the Soviet Army realized the war could not be won, their withdrawal (in resignation and frustration and ultimately, at least as claimed by the mujahideen of those days, in defeat) was only a matter of time.
- Tribal militias and gangs in Afghanistan often fight for those who pay best. This is advantageous for those who have funding available or can dole out other compensatory incentives. However, it also signifies that a given coalition

is often of an unstable and temporary nature. Currently existing military alliances with non-Northern Alliance militias can fall apart quickly if the other side will at some point be able to offer more money or a more promising future.

- The fighting against the insurgency takes place mainly in the southern areas of the country, which are almost exclusively inhabited by Pashtun tribesmen. Pashtun culture has as its center the concept of egalitarianism and cultivates the male ideals of possessing a fierce battling spirit and fighting prowess (with the exception of the lower artisanal caste as the special status of the sayeds or descendants of the prophet) as well as protecting the family's plot, the clan's and tribe's land and the females. These qualities/ideals are all linked to and define male honor symbolized in the sword and rifle (*tura/topak*). Western troops have been reported to violate basic principles contravening the tribal code of honor, for instance by searching houses entering into the harem/womens' quarters and raiding orchards, as well as (inadvertently) killing civilians. Even if they do not search houses any longer this doesn't make the past incidences unhappened.
- Strategically the experienced military insurgents potentially have an edge over anti-insurgent (Western and, also to some extent, ANA) troops on several counts: they have a religious belief in their mission to fight for Islam and against the presence of foreign military on their home soil, they know the terrain, they have been fighting under these conditions for up to two and a half decades, they speak the language of the locals³⁷ and the local population is in

³⁷ Many veteran Arab fighters are fluent in Pashtu for having lived more than two decades in Afghanistan. Many have intermarried with local Pashtun families and it can be surmised that some have even been recognized as fellow Pashtuns, by now (speaking the language, knowing and observing the code of honor, being Muslim are the three criteria which such individuals need to fulfill to qualify for being accepted as Pashtun).

many cases in a decidedly neutral position or shifting towards the Taliban (psychologically, the attacking Afghan and Western forces are consistently in the defensive when it comes to explaining and justifying civilian casualties in firefights against insurgents; the insurgents hide between and among civilians, in many cases against their will, however they are rarely the ones who kill the civilians with the exception of the suicide attacks that also habitually kill innocent bystanders). Those among them who are local Pashtuns are also fighting to revenge intrusions in their homeland and, in some cases, what they conceive as disrespect of their male and tribal honor. Finally, many enjoy fighting and crave for an opportunity to demonstrate their fighting prowess, while others may be eager to become martyrs. Any given combination of the above makes them determined, often battle-hardened opponents. All the above is combined with the factors that Taliban fight for a religious cause (and al Qaeda for a faith-based ideological cause), and the battle is being further charged with the jihad element (fighting foreign, Christian troops).

- The Pashtun society is a segmentary society. The tribal customs ask that any post-pubertarian male, to be a “real man”, consider himself worthy of being a leader and act as such. In tribal society, Pashtun leaders continuously have to prove their rank above the others; only exceptional leadership skills that remain unchecked and unrivalled will keep a tribal leader in his position, which explains why many traditional leaders or *khans* found it difficult if not impossible to maintain their leadership when challenged by Taliban and war lords, who were and are often better equipped than traditional tribal leaders.
- The ability to suffer is potentially more developed among the Taliban than among the Western nations. Psychologically, they are on the upswing since in a far better position and much stronger than six years ago when they were chased away from power and Kabul and driven out of Afghanistan. They do not have media that decry civilian and military victims; to the contrary, civilian

and military victims are confounded and all counted as martyrs. This potentially further increases the zeal of the fighters and society's support for the fight. The families of those fallen are amply rewarded by financial backers of the movement, which makes it easier for them to suffer a death. The large family size and polygamy typical for the tribal area (up to four wives at any given time, potentially taking the total well beyond four in cases of demise or divorce from a wife and up to ten children per wife), make it comparatively more sufferable for families to lose one or more of its members. Finally, the notion of years not doing much else except fighting does not bother the insurgents; time flows by and the insurgents are convinced that "the longer we are fighting, the better our chances of exhausting the determination of the infidels". Many troops and commanders literally don't have much else to do or if they do, often nothing as profitable and beneficial in the sense of their spiritual well-being, individual and tribal pride and reputation, finally directly and/or indirectly also financially (free board and room while fighting; compensation for their family when killed).

- The Pashtun tribe's male ideal is the warrior and fighter and thus, conflicts are often solved by violent means. But there are customary institutions of conflict regulation that allow ending a conflict in what is emically perceived as an honorable and thus, socially-sanctioned fashion. These avenues could be mobilized to initiate negotiations and broker a peace agreement. There are indications that the budding peace agreement of Musa Qala where NATO and Taliban agreed with local tribal elders to convert the district center into a no-fight zone, were undermined by both renegade Taliban and Western troops. NATO should pursue this avenue of peaceful conflict resolution and show wisdom and restraint when individual Taliban commanders try to destroy an agreement. As a trust-building measure, NATO should not have responded by

resuming war but by insisting on the agreement and asking the Taliban command to call the renegade commander to order.³⁸

124 JAGRA/JUGRA

A serious fight taking place between two groups of people in which bruising, wounding and killing occurs. JAGRA is an act that leads to further enmity. To bring truce and reconciliation JIRGA and MARAKA (tribal customary law court) must necessarily be convened. In tribal JAGRAS the severity of the act is so great that SPIN PATKEYAN (mullahs) will put black ceramic cooking pots or Qurans over their heads and go into the JAGRA field to call for a temporary truce until the MARAKACHEYAN (members of the tribal customary law court) may be called to bring about complete reconciliation. Subsequent to the above, MARAKACHEYAN or JIRGAWALS can bring either temporary or permanent truce (TIGA).

355 WALA/WALI

In Bajawar WALA or WALI means "provisional truce". When the mediation of the elders of the tribe brings provisional truce between the warring sides, it is called WALA or WALI. WALA or WALI is to provide good chances for TIEGA EKHODAL. WALA does not last more than a few days or a week at most. If in this time TIEGA EKHODAL is not effected, the JUGRA is resumed. After the second WALA the TIEGA EKHODAL must be effected, otherwise the JUGRA becomes very heated and bloody.

332 TIGA

TIGA, TIZHA and DABARA all mean "stone", but in tribal customary law they mean truce honored by both sides to a quarrel. In some places TIGA means the rules and regulations of JIRGA. The "Ahmadzai's tiga is very heavy". If someone breaks the truce (breaks TIGA) he will have to pay a very heavy TAWAN (penalty/fee). The ESA TIGA and the MUSA TIGA are two types of TIGA. For

³⁸ On August 3rd, 2007 the Taliban command stated that they would be willing to send emissaries for negotiations about the fate of the Korean hostages held captive by them, provided the UN would guarantee for their immunity and safe return. They said a preferred site would be a district in Afghanistan where the Taliban have a strong presence.

example, one will say “da Esa par tiga” or “da Musa pa tiga ra sara malumaway?” meaning “according to which TIGA, ESA or MUSA, shall we settle the matter?” The settlement decision of JIRGA the implementation of which is guaranteed through BARAMTA (pledge) is also called TIGA. As BAND or BANDUN conveys the meaning of the settlement agreement of MARAKA, TIGA conveys the same meaning in the case of JIRGA. There are two types of TIGA; temporary and permanent. Temporary TIGA can be for a very short time; for two or three days. Temporary TIGA can lead to permanent TIGA.

23 BAND

BAND means prevention and BANDAWAL is to prevent, to stop and to discontinue. In customs and usages it means to stop fighting, to prevent and to discontinue it and to effect reconciliation. BAND closely connotes the (ritual settling by way of) “stoning” (TIEGA DABARA and TIEGA EKHODAL) of enmity on which truce is founded. Among the Zadran tribe both BAND and TIEGA EKHODAL are in use. It seems that TIEGA EKHODAL is to end serious enmities and BAND is to prevent the continuation of less serious offenses. Both are effected by MARAKA. Din Mohammed Zadran told me that in Zadran tribes both TIEGA and BAND are in use. But Mohammad Hashim Alikhel informed me that in Ghilzai tribes of Pakteya TIEGA does not exist; only BAND is in common use.

29 BASHAL

BASHAL means "pardon". Every member of a tribe has the right to it. Every individual or group of a tribe can grant it to the encroachers upon his rights. The act of BASHANA is BASHAL. Usually BASHAL is given in the cases of murder. No cases of BASHANA in the case of assault on a woman have been found. In cases of such assaults and encroachments BASHANA is not granted. If someone were to grant BASHANA in such a case, he would lose face in his tribe. (...)

127 JIRGA

A meeting of a group of tribal men that has the authority to settle a dispute in a way acceptable to both sides. In common usage any meeting convened to investigate and settle tribal matters is called JIRGA. In this sense of the term JIRGA and MARAKA are synonymous. In the specific sense of the term JIRGA is

a large meeting in which the MASHRAN (elders) of the KHELs (a cluster of tribal branches) take part to investigate and settle important tribal problems. The MULLAS participate in JIRGAS as SPIN PATKEYAN to pray for the success of the JIRGA. NARKHEYAN knowing the rules of JIRGA participate in JIRGAS, too, of course. Besides the groups mentioned above, the common people can sit near the JIRGA to listen to the discussion. Every member of the JIRGA is called a SPIN GIERAY (white bearded) or MASHAR (elder). There is no chairman among the JIRGA members. All members of the JIRGA are equal. JIRGA is convened mostly in ZIARATS (grave yard of a tribe's ancestors, holy place) in the open space. The JIRGA members sit in a circle so that no one shall be considered privileged or powerful. Sometimes, when it is necessary, the JIRGA may convene in secrecy. No outsider may sit near the JIRGA then; if he still does, he will be heavily punished. The punishment ranges from shaving his mustache and beard to setting his house on fire and even execution. When the JIRGA is sitting nobody shall interrupt its business or try to disrupt it. Anyone hindering the JIRGA work is penalized according to the rules of JIRGA. When one side of JIRGA sees the decision of the JIRGA prejudicial to itself, the members concerned will express their dissatisfaction by hitting two stones against each other. This act is considered disruptive to the JIRGA work, but as a tradition it is still practiced sometimes in some places. On every historic occasion JIRGA is convened to reconcile the inimical tribes or to bring about an agreement among the various tribes concerning a decision on some important problem of the day. At the time of the formation of tribal unity among the Pashtun tribes in Afghanistan two very important historic JIRGAS were convened. The first was the Manji Jirga in which many elders of all tribes participated and assigned Mir Wais Baba to carry out a coup d'état against Gurgien to abolish the Persian colonial rule. The second was the Kandahar Sher-i-Surkh Jirga to elect Ahmad Shah Baba. The difference between MARAKA and JIRGA is that MARAKA is to investigate and settle problems of small importance. The members of MARAKA are elders of the various PSHA (PLARINA) of one KHEL. A JIRGA considers and settles problems of great importance and its members are the elders of various KHELs concerned. The JIRGA decision is binding on everybody and noncompliance is punished heavily (for example the house is set on fire). The Aryans had JIRGAS. When the Aryan society developed the stage of settled agricultural life, Jana and Jana Pada (the tribal war administrator) came into existence. Two JIRGAS were established: The members of Sakha were common people and the members of Samti were nobles. A certain collection of KHELs is called TABAR and the delegates of TABAR sit in JIRGAS to consider important problems. When a decision is reached, the members of the JIRGA will swear on MALGA (salt), TURA (sword) and the Quran. The ceremony is to put hands on the things mentioned and pledge to carry out the decision faithfully. When one participates in a secret meeting of JIRGA and reveals the JIRGA proceedings, he is punished by shaving his mustache and beard, setting his house on fire or executing him, depending on the importance of the case. Every tribe has a

meeting place for the JIRGA which is considered sacred. In some places flags fly over it. The seating place of the JIRGA is always an open space so that those who like to watch the open meetings of the JIRGA can sit around.

- According to Shari'a, as soon as the enemy stops fighting and signals interest in reaching a truce or peace agreement, a Muslim is obliged to lay down arms as well to initiate talks. The same applies to tribal Pashtuns who have to accept a settlement according to *nanawate*, if offered by the opposing side. In some areas of Afghanistan's south, councils of tribal elders as well as traditional leaders (*khan*) who used to be in control of southern Afghanistan's Pashtun communities have suffered a loss in power and prestige ever since the liberation struggle against the Communist regime began some three decades ago. Exclusively relying on them in trying to mediate will not always suffice but it is one avenue worth investing in.
- Offering the Taliban to surrender or else get captured or annihilated is not amenable to fostering the position of moderate elements willing to engage in negotiations about a common project of society and a jointly supported Islamic State. If they are asked to renege on their ideals and movement the Taliban movement has no incentive to cease the pursuit of its ideal project to oust the Western-backed Karzai regime and reclaim power. Entering negotiations should be considered rather sooner than later for the more military might is mobilized to fight the insurgency, the more the opposition will increase. Pursuing the military logic is thus counter-productive and ultimately self-defeating.
- For the greater region, a development strategy will need to be conceived that includes the tribal corridor on the southern side of the Durand line. Negotiations need to be held on neutral terrain. Germany might still be a strong contender for hosting such a conference, but with each day of Tornado air reconnaissance support provided for fighting operations, the chances of

being accepted by the Taliban for hosting such a conference dwindle. Opponents and enemies are being created among the Pashtun locals, who are well aware of the role that German reconnaissance air support plays in directing aerial attacks, that, although not intended, also lead to civilian deaths. NATO and the American forces are thus endangering a vital asset. Without this type of support the German role would still have been limited to the PRT-type non-fighting operations in Kunduz.

6.2. CHANNELLING ENERGIES THROUGH THE TRIBAL LENS OR PRISM - IDEAS TOWARD A BLUE PRINT FOR A PEACE CONFERENCE AND “NEW DEAL” FOR AFGHANISTAN

In (southern) Afghanistan, the security issue is closely intertwined with the poppy economy and mercenarydom. As long as no viable alternatives offering a profitable income are existent, daily labor for the poppy field and soldiers for militias and politico-religious groupings will always be in supply, compounding the ranks of religious zealots who have taken up arms for a cause. Without a minimum level of security, economic stability and sustainable social development (including the introduction of quality public health care and education services) in conservative, remote areas will likely remain absent for a long time.³⁹ Following the same logical pattern, a truce leading to a peace plan and reconciliation between the warring Afghan/Pashtun factions is dependent on the shared political, social and economic vision for the country; or, to be more precise, for the southern part of Afghanistan and the northern contested parts of Pakistan, including the NWFP, FATA, and Kashmir. Likewise, the implementation of such a

³⁹ For a comprehensive analysis of the interconnectedness of these issue, see Craig Naumann (2007; 2009).

vision depends on the peaceful resolution of the current antagonisms in political culture.

From early 2007 onwards, there have been a number of overtures on the part of the Afghan government to negotiate with Taliban representatives about a Peace Plan. After a much-publicized intelligence leak involving Western diplomats painting a gloomy prospect regarding the ability to militarily defeat the Taliban, General David D. McKiernan, USA (then the Commander ISAF and Commander USFOR-Afghanistan before General McChrystal replaced him) addressed the Atlantic Council in mid-November 2008 suggesting that the idea of fighters putting down their weapons and agreeing to support a legitimate constitution of Afghanistan is a very powerful incentive that ought to be pursued.⁴⁰ While Western forces are stepping up cross-border attacks (mainly, if not exclusively, at least for the time being, by drones and artillery fire) targeting the FATA and surrounding areas like the Swat valley, Pakistan's army has moved into the Pashtun tribal areas to take the fight to its enemy. The results is massive civilian uprooting and the destruction of infrastructure and livelihoods. Thousands of civilians were turned into IDPs in a matter of a few weeks, if not days. Admittedly, "terrorist infrastructure" is being destroyed but there is no way of telling if the militants are just being dislodged or seized. "Flushed out" can result in a controlled outcome or actually worsen the situation, if one cannot control or guide the direction of the spill and the related consequences and effects. Meanwhile, the talk about beefing up the strength of combined ANA and police forces to more than 200,000 heads is not waning.

Today, it is highly improbable that either the money or the popular support for a massive long-term commitment for a continuation of the current approach could

⁴⁰ David MCKiernan, Atlantic Council's Commander Series, November 18, 2008

be mustered by political and military Western leaders in their respective countries, given that such a commitment would be politically visible and highly controversial. Among the Taliban as well as political observers there is confusion about the actual motivation, justifications and root causes of the West's, and particular, US forces' presence in Afghanistan. Hypotheses differ wildly and are even contradictory. Is the driving force the desire to hunt down bin Laden and fight al Qaeda or is it really about fighting the Taliban to secure functioning Afghan state institutions? Is it about nation building or building a sovereign state, at the risk of actually weakening it? The waters become even murkier in that Western support to the rentier state has counterproductive effects regarding its effective self-sustainability and overall popular support. Discriminatory nation-building at the expense of inter-ethnic concord has so far alienated the most conservative-minded religious segments of Afghan society.

Rashid/Rubin wrote in late 2008: "The Great Game can no longer be treated as a sporting event for distant spectators. It is time to agree on some new rules."⁴¹ They go on to suggest that the West consider negotiating with those factions among the insurgents whose interests and objectives are locally or nationally confined, as opposed to those – like al Qaeda – that have a wider regional or even world-wide agenda and have shown the capability and willingness to (further) attack Western countries, be it in Europe or North America. While the suggestion not to automatically rule out talking to elements of the insurgency smacks of a more expansive "target group" than the term "moderate Taliban" which have so far often been referred-to as potential interlocutors by various Afghan and Western sources, the call for "new rules" is not sufficiently clear.

⁴¹ Foreign Affairs, November/December 2008: "From Great Game to Grand Bargain – Ending Chaos in Afghanistan and Pakistan".

Rashid/Rubin veil their comment in diplomatic code to the point of diluting what might have been their key message and state that “Talking with Taliban fighters or other insurgents does not mean replacing Afghanistan's constitution with the Taliban's Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan, closing girls' schools, or accepting other retrograde social policies”. What they fail to see or at least fail to clearly spell out and admit, is that concessions will need to be made to those interlocutors, since offering them to be part of the political competition provided they accept the Constitution, or else face annihilation, is very likely not good enough an incentive, even in the unlikely and self-defeating event of total withdrawal of foreign (and more specifically, Western) troops.

Since maintaining foreign forces in the country is a sine-qua-non for preventing a rehash of the early 1990's internecine fighting, and the departure of those very troops is a key tenet of the insurgents' demands, there will remain a stalemate as long as maintaining the presence of foreign troops cannot somehow be reconciled with the departure of the US and NATO. An answer to these seemingly irreconcilable positions consists in framing a “Marshall” Plan package or “New Deal” for the South in a different fashion from the one for the predominantly non-Pashtun, mainly northern, provinces, with Western forces securing the capital but non-Western, non-Christian army contingents forming a UN peace-keeping force deployed in the southern provinces of Afghanistan, replacing Western troops. An alternative scenario under such a dual-track approach might consist in keeping troops in the northern parts of the country while withdrawing them from the Southern districts that opted for Taliban rule. In those districts, joint forces of local tribal militias, Taliban, and possibly also ANA forces, could be formed. Those districts or provinces that prefer to live under Taliban rule, as determined under a referendum under international supervision and military protection, might even be offered the possibility of evolving and receiving support without the presence of ANA soldiers.

Either way, while there is indeed a need to agree on some new rules, Western decision-makers at some point might have to consider accepting that in reality, there is an endogenous set of traditional rules. This existing set of rules is the one that really counts for rural Pashtuns and logically should play a central role in deciding over the fate of tribal Pashtun Afghanistan and Pakistan. The existing local ethos and its rules are by far more adequate to solving the present logjam than any others. To argue that the *Pashtunwali* is only of concern for the Pashtuns is correct when it comes to the specific manifestations of this system. However, other Afghan groups living in the Afghan south (especially in the rural areas) have either become culturally assimilated or have very similar emic understandings of the notions of honor, the do's and don'ts affiliated with it and the ensuing penalties.⁴² Hence, while the corpus does still play a crucial role with regard to Pashtun self-identity the issue of the differentiation vis-à-vis other ethnic groups needs to be questioned if it is supposed to mean that other groups do not have equivalent moral values and behavioral prescriptions or sanction modi. While Pashtunwali is indeed the most prominent and reputed ethnic code, the core concepts as such are very much present among other ethnic groups and tribes, as well.

The Taliban will never simply surrender just because they are offered to participate in elections. This offer has been long-standing and is gradually

⁴² Cases of “righteous homicide” not persecuted by official police have occurred in the Tajik province of Badakhshan among rural Tajiks not accepting what was conceived as indecent, public courting (corresponding to the Pashtun concept of *gakh* which is an expression of *tura* but can easily be met with violence leading to death not necessarily followed by *badal/wrata* if considered as outrageously and unnecessarily bold and hence as falling under salem. – As an aside it should also be mentioned that the one group reputed to be the most uninhibited and non-complying with otherwise commonly shared moral standards of Afghanistan, are the kuchi nomads, who are mostly of Pashtun ethnicity.)

losing the limited appeal it might have had around 2003/4. Putting one's money on the *Pashtunwali* as the time-tested code of conflict regulation, as archaic as it may seem, has far better chances of brokering a peace-deal. Ignoring this option by insisting that rules of the sovereign Afghan state's public law be applied will likewise be ignored as has been the case in the past.

It is high time for foreign forces intervening in Afghan affairs to acknowledge that the Afghan tribal areas are far from lawless.⁴³ No term could be more misleading and exemplary of the fundamental culturally warped misreading of forces affecting and shaping the playing field of tribal Pashtun country. The Taliban were so successful not least because they were welcome as a force able to bring law and order (based on sharia and *Pashtunwali*) to Afghanistan... no doubt in many aspects an archaic law and order, but still preferable to the local Pashtuns facing chaotic lawlessness imposed by warlords bound neither by sharia nor *Pashtunwali*. Furthermore, *Pashtunwali* has traditionally been a component of Afghan statehood's juridical set-up, which relies on legal pluralism. Even today, Afghans in the southern provinces can choose among the different concepts of *Pashtunwali*, sharia and public secular law when engaging in a lawsuit.

Consequentially, designing procedural options about how "negotiations" with the current detractors of the regime in place could be framed would need to include a clear understanding signalled to the Taliban that an agreement about constitutional arrangements and local governance is indeed on the table, if need

⁴³ Mindless media coverage keeps repeating the term "lawless tribal areas" with reference to southern Afghanistan and north-western Pakistan (FATA). The self-referencing cycle does not only make the statement less wrong; unfortunately, it has the disadvantage that it clouds decision-makers minds and poisons public opinion. A google search of the term yields more than 20k hits.

be with differing solutions for different regions accepting some sort of a decentralization. Discussions would then flesh out the security as well as political arrangements. In addition, the design and implementation mechanisms for construction programs would need to be agreed upon. There would need to be a strong component of capacity building and financial support targeting administrative services even in the tribal areas, preferably based on local talent and the model of customary local councils (*shura/jirga*).

Administrative services would not necessarily need to be part of the standard Afghan set-up but could be part of “tribal agency” administrative services linked to the federal system to the extent necessary, just as is the case in other federal set-ups such as the United States, Germany, Ethiopia, India, or Pakistan.⁴⁴(In a sense, the set of issues are just another case of decentralization/provincialization/ownership/democratic participation.)

The above package could be coordinated with the development of an incremental phase-out plan for the Western military presence throughout the country including the Northern provinces, under the clearly stated condition that the phase-out will not be implemented unless certain indicators are reached which guarantee that those areas that opt against Taliban rule in the initial referendum will no longer require Western/ANA protection.

⁴⁴ German’s Southern-most state Bavaria enjoys the status of a “Free State” and has its own embassy at the EU in Brussels. Ethiopia has a tribal agency in the form of its SNNPR (Southern Nations’, Nationalities’ and Peoples’ Region). The individual states of the United States of America have their own legislation, political systems including State Houses of Representatives and Senates, and independent jurisdiction for non-federal matters. State police is in many cases not even allowed to cross into contiguous State’s territory when in “hot pursuit”. India as well as Pakistan (FATA!) have tribal agencies with special rights, privileges and institutions with limited federal presence and/or formal powers.

Delegating the responsibility for religious plus secular education to Taliban social development committees in the zones of their influence (mainly areas in the Pashtun south) would engage them in a joint reconstruction and state-building effort. The Ministry of Education together with civil society organizations could form technical working groups with representatives in the tribal Pashtun areas to work out modalities of teacher upgrading, school administration and related logistics. These efforts in the educational sector should be coordinated with cross-sectoral development initiatives: ANDS, i.e. infrastructure, water, roads, economic reconstruction. These measures could be coordinated with activities in the FATA, allowing the US government and other interested donors to spend the hundreds of millions of dollars set aside for development projects targeting these areas but never disbursed due to serious doubts over project viability and feasibility. – Parents and children would need to be guaranteed the choice of opting for a Taliban-run school or the ordinary public school model; the Taliban would need to concede that their model is accepted as one available alternative, but not the only option there is.

Education minister Farooq Wardak engaged in a policy of rapprochement with the insurgents by respecting local norms and values. He initiated behind-the-scene talks with local tribal elders, religious scholars and insurgent groups. They led to the reopening in early 2009 of eighty-one primary and secondary schools in southern provinces which had previously been closed due to insecurity.

This shows that nothing can be achieved against, but a lot can be won by collaborating with the conservative parts among the local population in rural southern Pashtun-dominated provinces. Thus, counterproductive delays can be avoided by opting for locally adapted pathways to enhanced access to educational opportunities instead of insisting on a standard "highway" solution consisting of one-size-fits-all specifications.

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